

MISSION

eMISSION-free HV and MV transmissSION switchgear for AC and DC

01.01.2024 – 31.12.2027

Call identifier: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-01-12

D1.1: Scenarios and vulnerabilities related to introducing SF6-free technologies in the grid

Lead partner: SINTEF

Authors: Salvatore D'Arco, SINTEF
Iver Bakken Sperstad, SINTEF
Thomas Treider, SINTEF
Luis Amaral, WAVEC
John Doherty, SNL
Matteo Maglio, G&W
Matias Vistnes, SINTEF
Erlend Sandø Kiel, SINTEF
Nina Sasaki Støa-Aanensen, SINTEF

Submission date: 30/06/2025

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Document history

Issue date	Version	Changes made / Reason for this issue
26.05.2025	1	First draft shared to partners for comments
30.06.2025	2	Final version submitted

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable summarizes the results of two tasks from Work Package 1 (WP1) of the MISSION project:

1. Task 1.1: Scenario definition for the future European power grid
2. Task 1.2: Ensuring grid resilience in the future European power grid

As outlined in the MISSION project description, the scope of this report is to describe relevant future scenarios (2030, 2050) and potential vulnerabilities in the European power system, with a focus on the technologies developed in the project and their impact on grid resilience. These technologies include new SF₆-free switchgear for High Voltage AC (HVAC), High Voltage DC (HVDC), and Medium Voltage DC (MVDC) systems.

The report provides a system-level context for the MISSION project's subsequent component development and testing. It explores how Europe's power system is evolving in response to climate goals and the push to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, especially through the replacement of SF₆-based equipment.

Chapter 2 highlights the need for large-scale deployment of renewable energy sources (RES), especially wind and solar, to meet 2050 EU targets. This transition demands extensive grid expansion but also more flexible grids and new operational approaches. HVDC is expected to support long-distance transmission, with MVDC emerging for urban and offshore use. Applications of superconductivity for power transmission are also discussed.

Chapter 3 projects a 40–60% increase in AC circuit breaker (CB) population by 2050 due to system expansion and aging infrastructure. Two strategies for transitioning to an SF₆-free circuit breaker population are compared: a gradual "Business as usual" scenario and an accelerated "SF₆-free by 2050" transition. The latter could cut SF₆ emissions by nearly 20% compared to the former but may require up to 75% more CBs if technology rollout is delayed, raising cost and implementation challenges. However, compared to the continued use of SF₆, both these strategies are found to reduce the emissions by approximately 60% by the year 2100.

Chapter 4 presents a qualitative study of grid resilience considering new switchgear technologies. No specific vulnerabilities were found for the SF₆-free equipment developed in the project. However, broader concerns such as vendor availability, limited TSO experience, and the complexity of HVDC system integration were identified. Risk mitigation strategies include enhanced collaboration, standardization, training, and HVDC CB development. Even with pessimistic assumptions, the grid reliability and resilience impact of new SF₆-free technology is likely to be minimal.

In conclusion, the shift to SF₆-free technologies and offshore energy systems involves trade-offs between environmental benefits, costs, and potential risks, but the work in WP1 found no major technical risks to grid reliability or resilience. Ongoing work will further assess economic and environmental implications to support evidence-based decisions by TSOs and policymakers.

1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable reports on the results of the following two tasks of Work package 1 (WP1) in the MISSION project:

- Task 1.1: Scenario definition for future European power grid
- Task 1.2: Ensuring grid resilience in the future European power grid

While the other technical WPs in MISSION focuses on SF₆-free technologies on a component level, the purpose of WP1 is to contextualise the work of these other WPs in a power system perspective. WP1 contributes to the overall project objective¹ through the following objectives:

- Assess the economic, environmental, and resilience/reliability impacts of technologies on a power system level (T1.1-T1.3)
- Provide guidance on how to implement an overall (power) system solution that includes the SF₆-free technologies developed in the project (T1.4)

The scenario definitions in this report will give inputs to the environmental and socio-economic impact analysis to be addressed in T1.3 and reported in D1.2. The roadmap and guidelines to be developed in T1.4 and reported in D1.3 will also use this report (D1.1) as input.

The scope of this report is summarized by the following brief specification of D1.1 in the MISSION project description: “Description of identified scenarios and vulnerabilities for the future European power system (i.e., 2030, 2050), focusing on the technologies developed in the project and potential impact on grid resilience.” The MISSION technologies include new SF₆-free switchgear technology for High Voltage Alternating Current (HVAC), High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC), and Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC). Broadly speaking, the purpose of the work has been to provide an overview of the expected structure of the system in the future, and then to shed light on what could be the role of new components in this system. This includes predicting their quantity and what requirements the system imposes on these components, and vice versa. Tasks T1.1 and T1.2 assume that SF₆-free technologies will be crucial also in case of the application of superconductive cables in the transmission system and the report includes considerations related to these aspects.

WP1 has a broader perspective than the other technical WPs in the sense that it considers the power system where the technologies from the other WPs should be implemented. To limit the scope of work, it has focussed on the aspects of the power system scenarios and vulnerabilities most closely related to the MISSION technologies. Furthermore, a methodological choice was made to combine qualitative analysis with a subsequent, narrower quantitative analysis: 1) Scenarios and potential vulnerabilities are initially analysed qualitatively to give a broad overview of trends and main issues. 2) Quantitative scenarios for the replacement of AC circuit breakers are generated, and a quantitative

¹ The overall objective of MISSION is to develop and demonstrate key SF₆-free switchgear components for the future AC and DC systems to enable emission-free energy transmission in a resilient and sustainable electric grid.

grid reliability and resilience analysis is carried out focusing on the replacement of HVAC circuit breakers.

The report is structured as follows. The scenarios from T1.1 are described qualitatively in Chapter 2, which first presents a broad overview of the future power system, before focusing on main drivers and key technologies relevant to the MISSION project. Chapter 3 presents quantitative scenarios for HVAC switchgear, including how much SF₆ leakage is prevented depending on the roll-out strategy. Chapter 4 presents the findings on identification and assessment of potential vulnerabilities in the future European power system, focusing on new HVAC and HVDC switchgear. Chapter 5 concludes the main part of the report. To keep the report concise, details are relegated to appendices: Appendix A summarizes relevant electrical analyses of superconducting systems to highlight their potential role in ensuring grid resilience and reducing the requirements for DC circuit breakers. Appendix B provides additional details on the calculation of scenarios for AC circuit breakers. Appendix C provides additional details on the methodology and data used in the assessment of grid resilience.

2 THE FUTURE POWER SYSTEM

The transition to a low-carbon energy system is paramount for Europe's climate strategy, aiming to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions while ensuring a secure and sustainable energy supply. This transformation is driven by an accelerated shift towards renewable energy sources (RES) and the modernization of electricity transmission networks to accommodate increased electrification and decentralized generation (DG). Key policy frameworks such as the European Green Deal, REPowerEU, and the EU's Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) are shaping the trajectory of this transition, targeting a high share of renewables in the energy mix and phasing out fossil-fuel-based power generation.

The transition to SF₆-free technologies in Europe's electricity transmission system is crucial due to SF₆'s extremely high global warming potential (GWP): 24 300 in a 100-year perspective [1]. In 2024, the updated EU F-Gas Regulation [2] set strict reduction targets and progressively banned SF₆ in new equipment where alternatives exist. Further reinforcing these measures, the EU Green Deal [3] introduced additional restrictions in 2022, mandating the complete phase-out of SF₆ in all new equipment of the electrical transmission by 2032. Replacing SF₆ with alternative technologies, such as air insulation or alternative gases, aligns with carbon reduction targets and ensures compliance with evolving EU regulations.

All projections indicate that Europe will experience a major increase in RES, led by wind and solar, from both large-scale farms and DG at the consumer level. At the same time, electrification in transport, households' consumption, and industry, and the growing energy demands of data centres will significantly raise electricity demand. To adapt, the transmission system must evolve, with HVDC playing a key role in interconnections and in integrating remote offshore wind parks. This transformation will also lead to a more meshed and dynamic grid, requiring possibly more frequent switching operations and a higher number of breakers. This transition could be challenging particularly in offshore environments, where space, environmental conditions, and accessibility are limiting factors, and in HVDC systems, which bring new technical requirements for protection and control.

The following sections explore these two main drivers of the green transition: the integration of renewables and DG (Section 2.1) and the adoption of SF₆-free technologies (Section 2.2). Together, these developments are reshaping the European energy landscape, fostering a more sustainable and low-carbon future.

2.1 Introduction of renewables and DG

The global energy transition is profoundly transforming the electricity sector, driven by the need for decarbonization, energy security, and independence from fossil fuels. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), *"there is no way to tackle climate change effectively without a surge in investment in clean power and infrastructure that significantly reduces coal-fired generation"* [4]. In this context, the introduction of RES plays a central role in reshaping the global energy system.

According to TYNDP 2024 Scenarios Report [5], Europe's energy supply will experience a major shift, with natural gas usage significantly decreasing after 2030 and being fully phased out by 2050. To compensate, renewable energy will dominate electricity generation. Figure 2-1 illustrates these

projections, highlighting the rapid growth of wind and solar power, with offshore capacity experiencing the highest multiplication factor among all sources, making its expansion crucial to achieving Europe’s renewable energy and climate goals.

Figure 2-1. Power generation mix for EU27 adapted from TYNDP 2024 scenarios [6].

While wind and solar will account for the largest share of production, offshore RES – primarily offshore wind – will contribute significantly, making up 18% of the electric energy produced in 2040 and 2050 [7]. Particularly, the Northern Seas (North Sea and Baltic Sea) alone are projected to exceed 330 GW of installed capacity by 2050, incorporating both bottom-fixed and floating technologies [8].

In 2023, wind and solar power generated 721 TWh, accounting for 27% of total electricity production in the 27 European Union member states (EU27) [9]. According to Figure 1, this share will increase significantly, reaching about 2000 TWh by 2030 (representing more than 50% of total production), between 3900 and 4500 TWh by 2040 (75%-85%), and up to 6000 TWh by 2050 (89%). If onshore wind and offshore wind are considered separately, solar will be the largest energy source in Europe by 2050, encompassing not only large-scale farms but also prosumers production.

In 2023, the EU’s total electricity production reached 2448.6 TWh [10], and it is projected to increase 2.8-fold (6800 TWh) by 2050. This surge, coupled with the significant expansion of renewables, will fundamentally re-shape the European electricity system. While large-scale farms will play a crucial role in decarbonization, their integration will require significant reinforcement of the transmission network to ensure stability and efficiency.

In addition to DG, the growing trend of electrification further underlines the need for grid expansion, not only to interconnect regions and manage fluctuations, but also to accommodate the increasing overall load. Meeting the future demand will require more generation capacity, but also an

improvement in both transmission and distribution networks. In particular, the integration of DG calls for a reinforced distribution grid to connect small-scale producers and consumers, while transmission remains paramount to export electricity from large-scale generation sites to consumption centres.

2.2 The role of DC

As Europe's power system evolves toward greater electrification, DC technologies are gaining traction. Improving interconnections between large electrical areas is considered critical for meeting growing electricity demand and supporting the transition from fossil fuels to RES [11]. With growing shares of renewable energy, rising demand for efficient transmission and distribution, and the proliferation of decentralised energy resources, DC offers technical and economic advantages that complement the traditional AC infrastructure. This section explores the emerging role of both high and medium voltage DC (HVDC and MVDC) systems, highlighting their contributions to the future grid and the challenges that must be overcome to enable their broader deployment.

2.2.1 HVDC

The declining costs of DC systems, particularly HVDC for transmission, make them an increasingly viable solution for long-distance power transport. According to [12], HVDC accounted for 2% of the transmission system in 2023, but it is expected to be around 10% by 2050, driven largely by HVDC export systems for offshore wind.

At present, most HVDC systems deployed in Europe follow one of two approaches: (a) point-to-point configuration, which connect remote generation sites to consumption centres; or (b) interconnectors that enable electricity trade between countries, such as NordLink, ElecLink, BritNed, and others shown in Figure 2-2 [11].

Both applications significantly reduce transmission losses over long distances (by approximately 43% over a 1000 km connection) [14]. Regarding offshore wind specifically, HVDC is increasingly being chosen for exporting electricity to shore due to an overall reduction in HVDC costs and its ability to unlock the potential for siting wind farms farther from the coast.

Another noteworthy application of HVDC systems is the back-to-back (B2B) HVDC station, which typically connects two neighbouring AC grids operating at different frequencies or without synchronisation, enabling a quick and flexible integration [14]. These installations, usually located at national borders, allow asynchronous systems to exchange power while maintaining independent operation and protection schemes.

While the above-mentioned HVDC applications are well-established and widely deployed, there is growing interest in a more ambitious concept: the overlay HVDC grid. This consists of a meshed DC transmission system superimposed on the existing AC backbone, designed to enable continental-scale, multi-terminal power flows. In theory, such grids could unlock access to vast offshore and remote onshore renewable resources, enable more dynamic and integrated electricity markets, and offer greater redundancy and resilience beyond what current point-to-point HVDC or AC systems can provide [11]. The Zhangbei HVDC project in China is frequently cited as a milestone towards this concept. Despite it has not yet become an overlay or backbone transmission system, it underscores a

Figure 2-2. North Sea and Irish Sea interconnectors. From 4C Offshore website [13].

significant step in this direction. In Europe, some ongoing EU co-funded initiatives – such as InterOPERA (<https://interopera.eu>) and HVDC-WISE (<https://hvdc-wise.eu>) – are exploring and advancing the concept of meshed HVDC networks.

Strengthening interconnections between large power systems is key to meeting rising electricity demand and supporting the transition to renewables [11]. As discussed, HVDC has strong potential to support this shift by enabling efficient, flexible, and long-distance power transmission. However, for Europe to pave this path, several challenges must still be addressed:

- DC protection technologies, including circuit breakers and other switchgears, are still constrained by high costs, complexity, and integration challenges in multi-terminal HVDC systems [15].
- Grid code harmonization is essential [11]. The absence of standardized operating and protection rules for DC networks is a major obstacle to interoperability.
- System-level validation is still lacking [11] as most HVDC systems operate in a point-to-point configuration, and there is little operational experience with large-scale, fully integrated HVDC overlays.

2.2.2 MVDC

Most developments stated for HVDC systems are also applicable to MVDC systems. While HVDC technology has the potential to be the backbone for continental-scale power transmission, MVDC has the potential to complement it for medium-scale, decentralised power distribution, bridging the gap between high-voltage transmission and low-voltage distribution.

MVDC operates typically in the range of 1.5 to 55 kV [16] and offers key advantages over AC systems at the same voltage level: higher efficiency, lower losses, no need for reactive power compensation, and simplified connection of heterogeneous generation sources such as solar PV, batteries, and fuel cells [17]. Moreover, MVDC allows easier control of power flows and voltage levels, making it attractive for grid segments with dynamic loads and sources. Finally, MVDC systems have the potential to enhance grid responsiveness to fluctuations in demand, supply, and fault conditions; some advantages are ultra-fast fault currents detection and isolation, reducing the risk of cascading failures and improving the overall reliability of the system.

Applications of MVDC have the potential to expand across multiple sectors, including:

- Data centres
- Industrial facilities
- Commercial buildings & campuses
- Electrical Vehicles charging
- Marine and rail systems
- Onshore and offshore collection systems

Despite progress, several challenges remain for large-scale deployment. There is still no widely accepted framework for standardising safe operating ranges, equipment stress testing, or interconnection practices. Protection schemes for MVDC grids remain complex, particularly when it comes to fault detection and rapid isolation. To operate safely in the interconnected grid environment, one of the major challenges is to install MVDC circuit breakers that are cost competitive, reducing the capital investment. Advancing robust, cost-effective DC circuit breakers and establishing clear regulatory guidelines are key areas for future research and implementation.

2.3 Technological trends for the future system

2.3.1 SF₆-free technologies for AC and DC switchgear

Switchgears are an essential element for the operation and the protection of the power systems. A main feature for switchgear is the capability to interrupt current and to ensure sufficient level of insulation to sustain the voltage. Most present switchgear design relies on gases to fulfill several tasks, such as:

- Providing dielectric insulation and sustaining high voltage
- Transporting away heat that is generated due to ohmic losses in the conductor when current flows

- In gas-circuit breakers, interrupting currents up to several tens of kiloamperes by cooling and quenching electric arcs that form between the breaker contacts during switching. (This is not applicable for switchgear with vacuum technology, where this arc quenching occurs in the vacuum chamber of the switchgear, not in the gas.)

Moreover, the lifetime of switchgear can often be up to 40 years, as can often be seen in today's substations. Hence the gas needs to be stable and keep its properties for a long time. For health and environmental reasons, the gas needs to be non-toxic (non-mutagenic and non-carcinogenic), with low ozone depletion potential, and of course with low GWP. Lastly, the gas needs to be in gas form over a broad range of temperature variations, at least -30°C – +50°C (sometimes even colder). Except from an environmental (and sometimes health) perspective, no alternative is found which can match SF₆ when it comes to technical suitability for switchgear applications. Consequently, SF₆-free technologies need to compensate by other means to become technically adequate, such as being filled with higher gas pressures and sometimes having larger dimensions. Their design must be optimized to match the corresponding existing SF₆-solutions where only part of the substation is renewed. Furthermore, this has led to a variety of solutions chosen by different manufacturers depending on application, business strategies and their own expertise.

Development of SF₆-free technology with the motivation of finding more environmentally-friendly alternatives has been ongoing for more than a decade, and several new technologies are already on the market and in operation in the distribution grid (up to 145 kV). For Europe's highest transmission voltage levels, at 420 kV, SF₆-free switchgear technology is still scarce, and no SF₆-free circuit breakers are yet in operation in Europe ². Furthermore, due to the high voltage and need for larger dimensions to electrically insulate the parts at different potential, these voltage levels have the largest amounts of SF₆ per unit. Consequently, finding reliable SF₆-replacements for the 420 kV transmission grid is imperative to be able to safely operate the European grid and reduce its greenhouse gas emissions.

In the MISSION project, an SF₆-free 420 kV live-tank (air-insulated) circuit breaker with vacuum technology will be developed and tested in the French and Norwegian grid. For each breaker, 62 kg of installed SF₆ are avoided. Based on DNV's energy transition outlook and their expected grid expansion needs, several thousand 420 kV circuit breakers are needed by 2030.

Vacuum circuit breakers are considered a mature technology for distribution voltage levels (< 52 kV), but not for transmission voltage level ≥145 kV, although installations with 145 kV circuit breakers in the grid are rapidly growing. (The first installation with a single-break 145 kV vacuum interrupter was energised in Germany in 2018 as a live-tank circuit breaker and Bergen, Norway in 2020 as a gas-insulated circuit breaker). One of the major design challenges when developing vacuum switchgear for the highest voltage levels is that the scaling of electric insulation as a function of distance is not linear, and there might be a limit to how high voltage one vacuum tube can be dimensioned for. In contrast, the electric insulation performance of gases scales more or less linearly with both distance and

² A few dead tank circuit breakers for 420 kV were put into operation in Connecticut, USA, in 2024. Moreover, some 420 kV circuit breaker projects have been commissioned in Europe. One example: <https://www.ssen-transmission.co.uk/news/news--views/2024/8/ssen-transmission-leads-the-way-in-sustainable-grid-infrastructure-by-being-first-to-implement-hitachi-energys-new-sf6-free-switchgear-technology/>

pressure. Another challenge with vacuum technology is that all heat from the current-conducting parts must be transported away from the breaker region through the solid parts, since heat cannot be transported through the vacuum. In gas circuit breakers, gas convection and conduction also contribute to disperse heat. The MISSION project will move the state-of-the-art of vacuum technology, by developing a double break vacuum circuit breaker for 420 kV and demonstrating it through type-tests and experience from grid-operation. The first generation of this new technology CB will have some reduced ratings compared to an SF₆-based circuit-breaker.

Many of the future offshore wind installations will be based on DC transmission to shore, up to 525 or 550 kV³. These installations will require an offshore substation to collect the energy from several wind turbines, convert and transform the energy to HVDC, before transporting the energy through HVDC cables to shore (and later, converting and transforming the energy back to AC). The offshore substations will be located on platforms, with limited space for grid components. Thus, compact gas-insulated switchgear (GIS) is preferred compared to air-insulated ones, to minimize the size of the switchgear on the platform. 550 kV DC GIS with disconnectors, earthing switches and instrument transformers (to measure voltage and current) are currently available on the market, but only with SF₆. One unit (bay) can contain up to 2.4 tons of SF₆ (yearly leakage rate around 0.1% per year), and there is a need to develop compact SF₆-free GIS to avoid future HVDC GIS installations with high greenhouse gas emission potential.

Another technology gap for future installations is the development of DC circuit breakers. Existing DC GIS cannot interrupt load or fault currents, and this is currently always done on the AC side of the grid. This is one of the main obstacles for developing multiterminal DC grids (off- or onshore). Breaking DC is more difficult than AC, due to the lack of natural current zero crossings. (For AC, zero crossings occur 100 or 120 times a second for 50 Hz and 60 Hz, respectively). Consequently, the switchgear must also first force the current down to zero. During short-circuit faults, this current can also rise very rapidly, and the response time for DC circuit breakers is strict, within a few ms, compared to tens of ms for conventional AC circuit breakers.

The MISSION project will develop two SF₆-free DC switchgear technologies to enable future grids for integration of RES while preventing SF₆-emissions from the grid components. The first is a 550 kV DC GIS (with backparts only, no circuit breaker) with nitrogen / oxygen insulation gas (80% N₂ / 20% O₂, GWP of the gas mixture is 0) for on- and offshore applications, with a significant potential for reducing SF₆-installations. This will be demonstrated to TRL 8 with a one-year demonstration in Germany.

The second is a 12 kV medium voltage (MV) circuit breaker for future multiterminal grids, including integration of superconducting technology. This MV breaker will be rated for 1 kA load currents and breaker operation time of a few milliseconds (demonstrated to TRL 6) and will be a valuable starting point for further DC circuit breaker development for higher ratings (larger currents or higher voltages) in the future.

³ 50Hertz has several offshore wind projects in their pipeline:
<https://www.50hertz.com/en/Grid/Griddevelopment/Offshoreprojects/Ostwind4>

2.3.2 Superconducting technologies

Superconductivity is a phenomenon whereby materials exhibit zero resistance when cooled below their critical temperature. High temperature superconductor (HTS) (77 K or -196.2 °C) tapes have been used to develop superconducting cables which leverage this characteristic to transmit power with zero losses over short distances. As of 2025, superconducting power cables are a mature technology at TRL 8/9. To demonstrate the technology superconductors have been deployed over short distances to provide a solution to urban grid congestion. Examples of superconducting cable systems which are deployed or currently in development are listed in Figure 2-3.

Ongoing research and development into superconducting cable systems is moving the technology towards the next generation, increasing operational range to allow for the connection of large-scale renewable generation sources, for transmission grid back bone reinforcement and high-capacity interconnection within existing grids. Capable of deploying in both marine and terrestrial environments, the next generation of superconducting cables brings the advantages of long-distance low loss transmission; high power density at lower operating voltages, smaller footprint and smaller rights of way when compared to conventional power cable technologies.

Recent Superconductor Projects			
2013		Ampacity, Essen	1km, 40MVA, 10kV, AC
2018		EU Horizon's 'Best Paths' Project	30m, 3.2GW, 320kV, DC
2019		Shingal, Seoul	1km, 50MVA, 23kV, AC
2021		REG, Chicago	62MVA, 12kV, AC
2024+		Superlink, Munich	12km, 500MVA, 110kV, AC

Figure 2-3. Recent Superconductor Projects

2.3.2.1 Superconducting cable system overview

A component view of an example next generation superconducting cable system (SCS) by SuperNode is shown in Figure 2-4. This SCS features a smooth bore inner cryostat to allow flow of liquid nitrogen (LN2), a HTS conductor electrically bonded to a protective copper shunt layer, multilayer wrapped insulation and a multi-layered outer cryostat. A component view of the SCS is shown in Figure 2-4. The primary functions of the cryostats are to house and insulate the conductor and facilitate conveyance of the LN2 coolant.

Figure 2-4. General Arrangement of the SuperNode SCS

Each section of SuperNode’s proposed superconducting cable has a design length of up to 5 km and is finished with an end cap. The end caps have been designed to integrate with other components such as electrical terminations, field joints and break out joints all of which are required to allow the SCS to operate at distances greater than 5 km. A proposed SCS operating at greater than 25 km is shown in Figure 2-5. A brief description of the components shown in the figure can be found in Appendix C Section 9.3.1.

Figure 2-5. Components of a superconducting cable system as proposed by SuperNode.

SCS can be deployed as part of an integrated offshore RES connection system including an onshore converter station and offshore collector station, addressing the industry trend towards 2 GW DC cables in continental Europe [18]. Scalable solutions of greater and lesser capacities can be deployed as required as illustrated in Table 1. A general arrangement of the connection system for an offshore application is illustrated in Figure 2-6.

Figure 2-6. Superconducting Offshore Connection System

The offshore connection system proposed in Figure 2-6 leverages DC wind turbines feeds power into array cables connected to an offshore DC platform. This DC platform has been shown in [19] to have a reduced footprint compared to a station with AC/DC power conversion plant. The array cable system voltage is transformed to 100 kV at the collector station and is transmitted to the onshore collector station by the bi-pole SCS. At the onshore station the DC power is inverted to AC before being transformed for transmission to the onshore AC grid. In the scenario illustrated in Figure 2-6, the SCS delivers a 2 GW power capacity, operating at a current of 10 kA and reduced system voltage of 100 kV compared to 525 kV HVDC systems using conventional cables. In [19] this lower operating voltage has been shown to reduce both the cost and footprint of infrastructure such as offshore collector stations and onshore converter stations.

The SCS can also be deployed for onshore applications such as high-capacity underground DC connections, again with available power capacity as shown in Table 1. For a 2 GW connection, a bi-pole superconducting cable system could be deployed using fewer cables compared to a system using XLPE insulated cables. For example, the proposed 525 kV Suedlink project in Germany requires two bipole circuits to transmit 2 GW, while by comparison an SCS operating at 100 kV would only require one. This results in significantly reduced right of way considerations for terrestrial transmission with a trench width of approximately 1 meter required for a multi-GW bi-pole system, as shown in Figure 2-7. By comparison the Suedlink project would require a minimum of two 1.3-meter trenches and a protection corridor of 16 meters [20].

Figure 2-7. Bi-pole superconducting cable trench

An SCS can be deployed with a range of operating characteristics maintaining high power density in an unobtrusive package. Expected operational ratings for a HVDC SCS provided by SuperNode are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Operating voltages of superconducting cable system

Operating Capacity (MW)	Current (kA)	Voltage (kV)
500	5	50
1000	5	100
2000	10	100
4000	10	200

2.3.2.2 Protection Characteristics of HTS Cables

In [21], SuperNode and University of Strathclyde have undertaken power system modelling of an onshore AC grid connected to high-capacity offshore windfarms through a DC grid system composed of meshed superconducting cables. The study analysed the behavior of the hybrid ACDC grid in the PSCAD software tool, and some advantages are listed below.

- Fault Current Limiting characteristics:** All superconducting cables have a critical current threshold, which when exceeded causes a quench in the cable. During a quench, the resistance of the HTS tape rapidly increases. As a result, when a fault occurs on a HTS cable the fault current will shunt into the parallel copper layer. This increases the impedance of the cable and will act as a distributed fault current limiter. The study revealed that during DC faults, this inherent fault limiting capability of SCS cables can provide “firewalls” around the fault and prevent it from propagating to the other healthy cables.
- Reduction in size DC circuit breaker architecture:** As superconducting cables naturally act as fault current limiters, the breaking capacity of protective devices can in theory be reduced. This reduces the size of AC protective equipment and in the case of DC can allow for alternative DC circuit breaker architectures to be leveraged.

2.3.2.3 DC circuit breakers for superconducting technologies

SuperNode has identified several DC circuit breaker (DCCB) technologies and addressed their suitability for integration into power transmission systems featuring superconducting cables, Figure 2-8 lists some topologies and conceptual diagrams. Several topologies of DCCB exist: mechanical (resonance), solid-state and hybrid breakers. Each with a different current breaking capacity and operating speed. -

A mechanical DCCB interrupts the current by breaking a mechanical switch. In typical HVDC circuits, mechanical DCCB’s may not be suitable due to their slow operating speed. However, in cases as presented above, technologies such as passive resonance current DCCBs may be suitable for switching faults in a superconducting cable system. Their slower breaking time would allow for the development of a quench in the superconducting cable resulting in a more desirable lower breaking current.

Solid-state DCCB’s make use of semiconductor devices such as IGBTs and MOSFETs to interrupt current. While they can interrupt faults very rapidly, they produce high losses due to current flowing

in the solid-state components during normal operation. As one of the main benefits of a superconducting cable is low loss bulk power transmission, this topology would not be suitable for integration into the SCS.

The hybrid DCCB combines mechanical and solid-state components. In normal operation current flows with very low losses. A fast-acting disconnecter is used to break the fault current and shunt it into a bank of solid-state components to interrupt the current flow. Hybrid breakers have been shown to interrupt high voltages and currents, with one such hybrid 80 kV HVDC breaker shown to be capable of interrupting fault currents of up to 15 kA against a returning voltage of 120 kV within 2 ms, and 12 kA in less than 1.5 ms. This would make hybrid DCCB's a suitable topology for integrating into the SCS. Hybrid DCCB is a mature technology and are currently in use on HVDC projects although at a lower current rating than required for SCS

Topology	Concept diagram	Conclusion for HVDC
Direct interruption using arc voltage		In railways -2-3kV, impossible for HVDC
Passive resonance current zero creation		For load switching, too slow for fault clearing
Active resonance current zero creation		Too slow with standard breakers. With vacuum high contact erosion
Solid state breaker		Very fast but very high losses
VSC assisted resonant breaker		Fast enough less power electronic switches, low losses
Hybrid breaker		Fast enough and low losses

Figure 2-8. DCCB Technologies

2.3.2.4 Role of superconductors in future grids

Table 2 gives an overview of connection types and use cases that describes the potential role of superconductors in the future power grids: a) point-to-point connections, b) high-capacity meshed grids, and c) parallel superconducting connections.

Table 2: Superconductor connection types and use cases

Connection Type	Applications	Benefits	Analysis
Point to Point	Connect large scale offshore renewables to onshore network Interconnectors between substations in urban environments Interconnectors between grid sections Interconnectors between national grids	High capacity Low footprint Built in additional capacity Fault current limiting	See appendix A: Section 7.1
High Capacity Meshed Grid	Provide multiple pathways for offshore renewables to connect to onshore network Act as part of an international offshore grid in an area such as the North Sea	Provides alternative routes for power flow Superconductors can be used to rapidly reroute power as their capacity is typically higher than operating value Fault current limiting properties can protective infrastructure requirements and complexity	See appendix A: Section 7.3
Parallel Superconducting Connections	Deployed parallel to existing powerlines Deployed to bootstrap grid sections that are already connected to increase capacity	Increased capacity in existing connections Improved reliability as superconducting cables be designed to carry additional current Can provide alternative power flow paths during faults	See appendix A: Section 7.4

2.3.3 Application of MISSION technologies

Figure 2-9 shows an overview of the three MISSION technologies: 1) HVAC circuit breakers, 2) HVDC switchgear and 3) MVDC circuit breakers. As illustrated in the figure, the technologies have applications for power grids both onshore and offshore.

Figure 2-9. Overview of mission technologies

Onshore and offshore electrical equipment differ substantially due to structural, environmental, and operational constraints. Structurally, onshore substations are built on solid ground, in most cases with ample space, allowing the use of Air-Insulated Switchgear (AIS). In contrast, offshore substations must be installed on top of platforms where space comes with a premium, requiring more space-efficient insulation systems (such as Gas-Insulated Switchgear – GIS) and compact equipment to reduce weight and footprint. Onshore substations, switching stations, conversion stations and transmission systems are easily reachable by ground crews, allowing regular maintenance and inspections. Offshore access is limited by sea and weather conditions. Due to harsh climate conditions like humidity and exposure to salt water, offshore equipment requires higher protection against corrosion and is designed to minimize maintenance needs, though when maintenance is necessary, it can be logistically complex and costly. Also, due to lack of accessibility, offshore systems demand remote monitoring and more automated control systems.

To further explore these distinctions and shed light on different MISSION technologies and their applications, the following two sections compare onshore vs. offshore systems and HVAC, HVDC and MVDC systems, focusing on the different characteristics of each combination.

2.3.3.1 HVAC systems

HVAC systems are the standard for electrical power transmission over long distances, typically at voltages above 100 kV. They are widely used in both onshore and offshore applications due to their compatibility with existing grid infrastructure.

Onshore. One of the key efforts is the replacement of existing SF₆-based HVAC circuit breakers with environmentally friendly, SF₆-free alternatives. To achieve this, most essential components need to be re-designed, re-enforced, or completely exchanged to eliminate the use of SF₆ gas. The MISSION project aims at developing a new 420 kV circuit breaker. In addition to replacing equipment in existing systems, new HVAC circuit breakers will be deployed for upcoming 420 kV substations. These include newly constructed onshore stations that play a crucial role in connecting the onshore grid to an offshore HVDC grid. SF₆-free circuit breakers will most certainly be introduced progressively across a variety of grid components. In the short term – within the next 3 to 5 years – first-generation SF₆-free breakers will be technically suited for use with power lines and transformers. However, they are not yet capable of reliably handling the specific requirements of capacitor banks and shunt reactors. These more demanding applications are expected to be supported in a later phase. Finally, the deployment of HVAC SF₆-free circuit breakers extends to new onshore renewable energy projects, including wind and solar farms.

Offshore. With regards to operational voltage, different levels are used depending on the scale and purpose of the offshore connection. A voltage level of 132 kV is commonly found in earlier offshore windfarms export systems but, with the rise in turbine capacity, 132 kV is now also being considered for intra-array cabling. 150-155 kV is typically chosen for medium-scale projects, while 220 kV is increasingly adopted for larger farms or longer transmission distances. Choosing 220 kV can reduce the number of export cables needed. However, the higher voltage level also entails greater equipment costs and more complex substation design. In terms of current capacity, and therefore power capacity, HVAC subsea cables are typically limited to 800-1000 A (phase-current) due to thermal constraints. This limitation arises because the cables are usually buried up to 3 meters in the seabed to minimize the risk of damage, which restricts heat dissipation. As a result, a single 220 kV export cable can usually transmit around 350 MW. To accommodate larger generation capacities, such as those from 1 GW-scale windfarms, multiple subsea cables (often three or more) are installed in parallel. An additional relevant application case would be HVAC circuit breakers for new energy islands/hubs designed as AC systems/stations.

2.3.3.2 HVDC systems

As introduced in 2.2.1, HVDC systems are increasingly used in Europe for long-distance transmission – both onshore and offshore – due to their high efficiency, controllability, and declining costs from technology development. Applications include point-to-point interconnectors, offshore wind export systems, B2B converters between asynchronous AC grids, and, in the future, meshed overlay or offshore HVDC networks.

Onshore. The development of a high-voltage direct current (HVDC) "backbone" grid is a key strategy for reinforcing the onshore power system. This backbone infrastructure could enhance the

controllability of both power flow and reactive power and better respond to fluctuations in demand and supply while improving overall stability. However, the relevance of HVDC circuit breakers within this context depends significantly on the design of the grid. In cases where the HVDC system remains point-to-point rather than forming a meshed or multi-terminal configuration, dedicated HVDC circuit breakers are typically not essential. For such simpler systems, protection of the overall network can be effectively and economically achieved with conventional circuit breakers on the AC side. These AC-side breakers offer a well-proven and cost-efficient solution for system protection, making them the preferred choice in point-to-point HVDC applications.

Offshore. Most recent HVDC installations use bipolar configurations with voltage ratings reaching up to ± 500 kV [22]. For example, Dogger Bank Windfarm, in the UK, uses VSC technology with voltages of ± 320 kV [23] and approximately 2000 A per pole, reaching 1.2 GW per link [13]. The offshore wind market is expected to push these numbers even higher by 2030, with the development of new HVDC systems operating at ± 525 kV and capable of transporting up to 2 GW per link [18] [24]. Subsea HVDC cables can carry continuous currents up to 1500-2000 A, depending on burial conditions and conductor type. Although similar thermal constraints apply (typical burial depths of 1-3 m limit ampacity), DC cables are not affected by charging currents, making them more efficient over long distances. Losses are typically around 3% per 1000 km, significantly lower than HVAC alternatives [14].

2.3.3.3 MVDC systems

Medium-voltage direct current (MVDC) systems are gaining traction as a flexible and promising solution for both onshore and offshore power applications, especially where traditional AC systems fall short in terms of efficiency, space, or control.

Onshore. MVDC technology is increasingly being explored for use in high-demand environments where space is limited or efficiency is critical. Urban areas and industrial zones, where expanding the grid is challenging due to space constraints, are ideal candidates for MVDC deployment. Additionally, MVDC is well-suited for large-scale solar photovoltaic (PV) installations, offering reduced transmission losses and simpler infrastructure over long distances compared to AC systems. The growing need for electric vehicle (EV) fast-charging stations also highlights the potential of MVDC, as it supports compact, high-capacity energy delivery. Another key application is in data centers, where MVDC can enhance reliability and efficiency while minimizing the need for multiple AC-DC conversions. Furthermore, superconducting MVDC cables are being considered for a future onshore DC “backbone” grid, which could significantly boost power transfer capacity and reduce losses thus strengthening the grid and supporting renewable energy integration.

Offshore. Currently, MVDC circuit breakers are still in the very early stages of technological maturity. They are scarce, costly, and physically large, which presents significant challenges for offshore applications where space, weight, and reliability are critical constraints. In parallel, superconducting MVDC links could offer efficient transmission for offshore energy systems, providing benefits similar to high-voltage DC (HVDC) systems but at a medium-voltage scale. These systems are particularly useful for short-distance, high-capacity transmission where space and weight are limited. In offshore wind farms, MVDC is being evaluated for use in collection grids. Compared to traditional AC systems,

MVDC networks can reduce power losses over long distances and simplify cable layouts, making them a more efficient and scalable option for large wind projects.

2.3.3.4 Overview of applications

The discussion above of application areas of the MISSION technologies (420 kV HVAC circuit breakers, 550 kV HVDC switchgear (that are not circuit breakers) and 12 kV MVDC circuit breakers) can be summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Overview of application areas of MISSION technologies.

Location	Voltage type	Application area	Application of MISSION technology
Onshore	HVAC	Onshore transmission	Replacement of existing SF6-based 420 kV HVAC circuit breakers with new SF6-free circuit breakers; new 420 kV HVAC circuit breakers for grid expansion
Offshore	HVAC	Offshore wind farm	(New HVAC circuit breakers will likely be at lower voltage levels than 420 kV)
Onshore	HVAC	Onshore wind or solar PV farm	(New HVAC circuit breakers will likely be at lower voltage levels than 420 kV)
Onshore	MVDC	DC collector grid for onshore wind or solar PV farm	New 12 kV MVDC circuit breakers
Onshore	MVDC	DC distribution grid	New 12kV MVDC circuit breakers
Offshore and onshore	HVAC and HVDC	Hybrid AC-DC offshore-onshore grid	New 420 kV HVAC circuit breakers and new 550 kV switchgear in a new power system offshore
Offshore or onshore	MVDC	Superconducting transmission	MVDC circuit breakers for MVDC superconducting cables. This may include cables for onshore DC “backbone” grid (reinforcement, as part of “Onshore transmission”) and/or offshore DC links (part of “Offshore wind farm” and “Hybrid AC-DC offshore-onshore grid”).

3 TRANSITIONING TO AN SF₆-FREE CIRCUIT BREAKER POPULATION

The EU F-Gas Regulation [25] is a comprehensive directive that goes beyond the electricity sector, laying the foundation for the phase-down of fluorinated gases (F-gases) across multiple applications. It explicitly highlights the extremely high GWP of SF₆ (24 300 CO₂-equivalents) and signals the growing availability of alternative technologies in different sectors. In 2022, the European Green Deal [3] and the Fit for 55 Package reinforced this framework, proposing that SF₆ should only be used in new transmission system equipment where no suitable alternatives exist. According to the European Commission, this strengthened proposal is expected to deliver greenhouse gas (GHG) reductions, with a great contribution through the enhanced phase-out of SF₆ in electrical transmission infrastructure.

This chapter presents the findings of MISSION Task 1.1 on scenario definitions for the future European power grid. Specifically, the present chapter provides estimates of the present-day population of AC circuit breakers (including AIS, GIS and SF₆-filled instrument transformers) in Europe along with scenarios for its future development. Two strategies for transitioning from today's SF₆-based population to an SF₆-free population are compared, both with respect to their economic impact – assessed indirectly through the number of new circuit breakers needed by 2050 – and their impact on the total emissions of SF₆. To fully illustrate the emission reduction potential of the two strategies, a baseline calculation based on the continued use of SF₆ is also performed.

In addition to the results in this chapter, appendix B provides further details on methodology and input data.

3.1 Present-day population of AC circuit breakers in Europe

To estimate the present-day population of circuit breakers in Europe, the Open Street Map database has been used as the main source of network data. The database provides an openly available overview of lines and substations across Europe. This has been combined with typical switchgear configurations for substations and lines at different voltages, which have been determined in collaboration with four MISSION TSOs, in order to estimate the population of circuit breakers. This exercise has been done for Norway, Germany, France, and Spain, and extrapolated to Europe based on the transferred electricity amounts per year (TWh load per year). Since the actual grid structure and therefore the number of AC circuit-breakers of each European country may differ, the extrapolation based on transferred electricity amount has to be considered as a rough estimation. Due to the implementation of renewable energies and a resulting change of the grid structure as well as an adapted operating mode of the grid, the effects of redispatch and load balancing will also further increase the number of AC circuit-breakers in some single countries even if the amount of total transferred electricity will remain nearly constant.

The registration of distribution lines and substations is very sparse in the Open Street Map database, and therefore a different approach has been used to obtain MV estimates. T&D Europe developed estimates for the European MV (up to 52 kV) population of switchgear, and their estimates for MV primary switchgear have been used [26].

Table 4 shows the estimated circuit breaker population. The numbers for Norway, Germany, Spain, and France have been rounded to the nearest 50. All calculations presented in this chapter are based on these four countries, scaled to represent Europe using a factor of 2.5. The last column in the table shows the resulting estimate for Europe, rounded to the nearest 1 000. For MV, the value is obtained directly from T&D Europe’s estimates and therefore not given for each individual country.

See appendix B for details on the properties of the present-day population, such as SF6 contents and age distribution.

Table 4: Estimated present-day circuit breaker population

Voltage	France	Germany	Norway	Spain	Europe
$U \leq 52 \text{ kV}$	-	-	-	-	1 500 000
$52 \text{ kV} < U \leq 75 \text{ kV}$	8 800	150	1 550	2 750	33 000
$75 \text{ kV} < U \leq 145 \text{ kV}$	3 100	20 600	2 500	2 950	73 000
$145 \text{ kV} < U \leq 245 \text{ kV}$	4 700	1 450	0	2 000	20 000
$245 \text{ kV} < U \leq 300 \text{ kV}$	0	0	800	0	2 000
$300 \text{ kV} < U \leq 420 \text{ kV}$	1 350	2 400	650	1 350	14 000

3.2 Future circuit breaker population growth

The future growth in circuit breaker (CB) population is assumed to be roughly proportional to the increase in yearly load in the power system. ENTSO-E’s Ten Year Network Development Plan (TYNDP) provides scenarios for this parameter [5]. The TYNDP scenario named “Distributed Energy” is used to estimate the overall circuit breaker population growth, with some adjustments made based on the MISSION TSOs’ own analyses. In Germany, the main driver for a growth in CB population is the restructuring of the transmission system towards one with distributed generation, but one does not foresee a large growth in the amount of transferred electricity per year. Germany’s transmission-level CB population is therefore given a different growth curve, with a rapid increase in the next 10-15 years and a more modest increase after 2040.

Figure 3-1 shows the resulting population growth estimated for the European circuit breaker population. The distribution and transmission levels are projected to grow by 43% and 56%, respectively, with the most rapid growth estimated to take place between 2030 and 2040.

Figure 3-1. Projected growth of the circuit breaker population at the distribution level (≤ 52 kV) and the transmission level

3.3 Strategies for transitioning to an SF6-free population of circuit breakers

The number of circuit breakers needed in the future, both for replacing aging circuit breakers and accounting for system expansion, depends on two main factors: 1) the overall population growth, as presented in Section 3.2, and 2) the pace at which the existing population of circuit breakers is decommissioned (including decommissioning due to faults). Two strategies for transitioning from the present-day SF6-based circuit breaker population to an SF6-free population have been defined, showcasing the impact of two fundamental approaches TSOs and DSOs can take towards this transition.

In the strategy named “Business as usual”, it is assumed that CBs are replaced when they reach their natural end-of-life, and that all new circuit breakers added beyond a certain year are SF6-free. (2026-2032 is assumed as a default value depending on the voltage level, see Table 5.) For the voltage levels where SF6-free alternatives are already available and utilized in some capacity, the SF6-free share of the population is ramped up to reach 100% by the year indicated in Table 5 .

In “SF6-free by 2050”, SF6-based circuit breakers are forced out of operation by 2050. This forced extra decommissioning begins when SF6-free technology becomes available, and “Business as usual” is followed until then. SF6-free CBs in operation today and in the future will be allowed to reach their end-of-life naturally and their replacement will be governed by the “Business as usual” strategy. The “SF6-free by 2050” strategy is the most ambitious, and TSOs such as Statnett and National Grid have stated that they will become SF6-free by 2050.⁴

Table 5: Availability of SF6-free circuit breakers

Voltage	SF6-free alternatives become widely available
$U \leq 52$ kV	2026
52 kV $< U \leq 75$ kV	2028
75 kV $< U \leq 145$ kV	2028
145 kV $< U$	2032

⁴ See <https://www.nationalgrid.com/us/net-zero-plan/eliminating-sf6-emissions> and <https://www.statnett.no/om-statnett/barekraft/klima/> (in Norwegian). Accessed 2025-04-10.

Note, however, that the “Business as usual” strategy also represents a relatively ambitious approach, given that all circuit breakers commissioned after the years indicated in Table 5 will be SF6-free. The timeline implied by Table 5 is in line with the requirements set by the EU and with assessments by TSOs and manufacturers in MISSION. Furthermore, several TSOs have committed to the even more ambitious “SF6-free by 2050”. For comparison, the impact of the continued use of SF₆-based circuit breakers will be considered towards the end of the chapter.

None of the MISSION partners see the supply of new SF₆-free circuit breakers as an issue, but there are practical and economic obstacles to overcome. One key bottleneck is that a limited number of circuit breakers can be commissioned per year, representing an important obstacle in committing to the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy. In some countries with a very large number of existing SF₆ circuit breakers it is currently not possible to exchange 100% of all SF₆ CBs by 2050 due to a lack of assembly and commissioning resources. In addition, there are economic obstacles such as depreciation over a 40-year operating life. Here, the economic boundaries and the regulatory framework in these specific countries have to be adapted in order to promote the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy.

3.4 Circuit breaker demand towards 2050

Figure 3-2 shows the projected number of circuit breakers required towards 2050, both on a yearly basis and cumulatively, when following the “Business as usual” strategy. By comparing these numbers to the present-day population in Table 4 it can be seen that the number of circuit breakers required cumulatively by 2050 is greater than the entire present-day population. Although the population as a whole grows by 40-60%, many circuit breakers currently in operation will have to be replaced.

Figure 3-2. Number of circuit breakers commissioned in the future with the "Business as usual" strategy

Figure 3-3 shows the impact of following the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy instead. Compared to Figure 3-2, it is clear that more circuit breakers will be required with this strategy, an expected consequence of decommissioning functioning circuit breakers prematurely. The effect is smallest for MV where a large portion of the present-day population is SF₆-free already, and the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy increases the number of required circuit breakers by approximately 10% here. For higher voltages, however, the present-day population is based on SF₆ technology, and SF₆-based alternatives are foreseen to become available at a later time. Therefore, the number of circuit breakers required with the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy increases by 30-50% in for voltages above 52 kV.

Figure 3-3. Number of circuit breakers commissioned in the future with the "SF6-free by 2050" strategy

3.5 SF₆ inventory and emissions

The estimated present-day inventory of SF₆ is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Estimated present-day SF₆ inventory in Europe (AIS and GIS circuit breakers and instrument transformers)

Voltage	SF ₆ in AIS (tonnes)	SF ₆ in GIS (tonnes)	SF ₆ in total (tonnes)
<i>U ≤ 52 kV</i>	250	1 410	1 660
<i>52 kV < U ≤ 75 kV</i>	410	410	820
<i>75 kV < U ≤ 145 kV</i>	1 620	2 750	4 370
<i>145 kV < U ≤ 245 kV</i>	660	1 690	2 350
<i>245 kV < U ≤ 300 kV</i>	120	290	410
<i>300 kV < U ≤ 420 kV</i>	1 560	3 410	4 970
Total	4 620	9 960	14 580

Figure 3-4 demonstrates how the SF₆ inventory in AC circuit breakers will develop with each of the two decommissioning strategies. With the "Business as usual" strategy the inventory reaches zero around the year 2080, while it by definition reaches zero in 2050 with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy. The initial decrease is largely driven by the natural decommissioning of old, SF₆-rich CBs with high SF₆ contents, replaced by state-of-the-art components with much lower SF₆ contents. Therefore, the SF₆

Figure 3-4. Development of the SF6-inventory with the "Business as usual" strategy (top) and the "SF6-free by 2050" strategy (bottom)

inventory decreases even before SF₆-free alternatives have become available. Once SF₆-free options become available, however, the decrease accelerates.

The effect of this process is that the total leakage rate also decreases over time. Figure 3-5 shows that the leakage rate drops from 0.7% today and eventually reaches 0.3%, which has been assumed to be the best attainable future leakage rate. Although the leakage rate develops very similarly with the two strategies, it drops faster with the "Business as usual" strategy. This may appear counterintuitive, but a large part of the circuit breakers that must be prematurely decommissioned with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy are relatively new with low leakage rates. Therefore, as the forced decommissioning begins, it is mostly new circuit breakers which are decommissioned, effectively increasing the average leakage rate of the remaining population of SF₆-based breakers. The effect is however quite subtle, and the overall emissions with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy are still significantly lower due to the smaller inventory of SF₆.

Figure 3-5. Development of the SF₆ leakage rate (operational leaks only) with the "Business as usual" strategy (top) and the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy (bottom)

While the SF₆ inventory end emissions reach zero in 2050 with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy, they persist until 2080 with the "Business as usual" strategy. To compare the overall emissions of SF₆ with the two strategies, the timeline must therefore be extended beyond 2050. Figure 3-6 shows the emissions of SF₆ with the "Business as usual" strategy on a yearly and cumulative basis, separating between constant operational leaks and end-of-life emissions occurring during decommissioning of the circuit breakers and recycling and disposal of the SF₆ gas. Overall, the emissions decrease over time as the inventory decreases, and almost 90% of the total emissions occur by 2050. Approximately 10% of the total emissions stem from end-of-life emissions.

For the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy, all the emissions, shown in Figure 3-7, occur by 2050. While the operational leaks are lower with this strategy, the total end-of-life emissions remain the same as for "Business usual". The end-of-life emissions are, however, compressed over a shorter period of time, leading to higher end-of-life emissions by 2050 with this strategy. As a result, despite this strategy having lower operational leaks, the total emissions by 2050 are just 9% lower than with "Business as usual" strategy. However, by the year 2100 the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy has eliminated 18% of the total emissions seen with the "Business as usual" strategy. See Table 7.

Figure 3-6. Development of the SF₆-emissions with the "Business as usual" strategy

Figure 3-7. Development of the SF₆-emissions with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy

Table 7: SF₆ emissions by 2050 and 2100 with the two decommissioning strategies (GWP = 24 300)

Strategy	Total emissions by 2050		Total emissions by 2100	
"Business as usual"	1520 t SF ₆	36.9 Mt CO ₂ -eq	1680 t SF ₆	40.8 Mt CO ₂ -eq
"SF ₆ -free by 2050"	1380 t SF ₆	33.5 Mt CO ₂ -eq	1380 t SF ₆	33.5 Mt CO ₂ -eq

3.6 Impact of delayed implementation of SF₆-free technology

Both decommissioning strategies will be affected by the availability of SF₆-free circuit breakers in the future, and a delay in the availability or implementation of this technology can have significant impact on the projected results. Although the transition from SF₆-based to SF₆-free circuit breakers is making good progress, this section aims to illustrate the impact of a delayed transition and highlight the importance of keeping the timeline assumed in the previous analyses.

Consider first the future circuit breaker demand in the case where SF₆-free circuit breakers become available or implemented 5 years later than previously assumed (see Table 5). Figure 3-8 shows the future circuit breakers required with the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy and compared to the base case results in Figure 3-3, the total number increase by approximately 5% for MV and 10-15% for the other voltage groups. The maximum number of circuit breakers required on a yearly basis also increases due to the delay, making the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy a greater practical challenge to implement.

The number of circuit breakers required with the “Business as usual” strategy is not affected by the delay.

Figure 3-8. Number of circuit breakers commissioned in the future with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy and a 5-year delay on the availability of SF₆-free circuit breakers

Figure 3-9 shows the resulting SF₆ inventory with a 5-year delay for the SF₆-free technology. Compared to the previous results, the impact is not significant, and the inventory still decreases naturally due to new, state-of-the-art circuit breakers having much less SF₆ than older circuit breakers.

Figure 3-9. Development of the SF₆-inventory with the "Business as usual" strategy (top) and the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy (bottom), given a 5-year delay on the availability of SF₆-free technology

The SF₆ emissions are also affected by the delayed availability of SF₆-free technology. Figure 3-10 and Figure 3-11 show the emissions, and Table 8 summarizes the change compared to the results without delays (i.e., from Section 3.5). The delay increases the total emissions by approximately 10% and 15% for "SF₆-free by 2050" and "Business as usual", respectively.

Figure 3-10. Development of the SF₆-emissions with the "Business as usual" strategy and a 5-year delay on the availability of SF₆-free technology

Figure 3-11. Development of the SF₆-emissions with the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy and a 5-year delay on the availability of SF₆-free technology

Table 8: Total emissions of SF₆ by 2100 with and without a 5-year delay in availability of SF₆-free circuit breakers (GWP = 24 300)

Strategy	Total emissions by 2100 without delay		Total emissions by 2100 with 5-year delay	
"Business as usual"	1680 t SF ₆	40.8 Mt CO ₂ -eq	1930 t SF ₆	47.0 Mt CO ₂ -eq
"SF ₆ -free by 2050"	1380 t SF ₆	33.5 Mt CO ₂ -eq	1510 t SF ₆	36.7 Mt CO ₂ -eq

3.7 Impact of continuing the use of SF₆ in circuit breakers

Both the “Business as usual” strategy and the “SF₆-free by 2050” strategy results in quite significant reductions of emissions of SF₆. To fully highlight this, the impact of not transitioning to an SF₆-free circuit breaker population will be calculated. It is assumed that the ratio of SF₆-based to SF₆-free circuit breakers remain as it is today, but that all circuit breakers commissioned in the future are state-of-the-art technology with minimal SF₆ contents and leaks. Circuit breakers are allowed to reach their end of life naturally, so apart from the emissions the results are identical with the “Business as usual” strategy.

While the SF₆ emissions associated with this strategy remain active indefinitely, the year 2100 is set as a cut-off in the calculations to enable comparison with the previous analyses. The circuit breaker population estimate from section 3.2 is only defined until 2050, so an extrapolation must be made to capture the emissions between 2050 and 2100, which are believed to be significant with this strategy. As a conservative estimate, the circuit breaker population is assumed to remain constant from 2050 and onwards.

Table 9 shows the total emissions with a continued use of SF₆. The emissions with each of the two transitioning strategies are repeated for convenient comparison. By 2050, the two strategies “Business as usual” and “SF₆-free by 2050” reduce emissions by 17% and 25%, respectively, compared to the continued use of SF₆. By 2100, those emission reductions have increased to 58% and 65%.

Table 9: SF₆ emissions by 2050 and 2100 with the two decommissioning strategies and the continued use of SF₆ (GWP = 24 300)

Strategy	Total emissions by 2050		Total emissions by 2100	
Continued use of SF ₆	1830 t SF ₆	44.5 Mt CO ₂ -eq	3980 t SF ₆	96.6 Mt CO ₂ -eq
“Business as usual”	1520 t SF ₆	36.9 Mt CO ₂ -eq	1680 t SF ₆	40.8 Mt CO ₂ -eq
“SF ₆ -free by 2050”	1380 t SF ₆	33.5 Mt CO ₂ -eq	1380 t SF ₆	33.5 Mt CO ₂ -eq

4 RESILIENCE AND VULNERABILITY

This chapter presents the findings of MISSION Task 1.2 on identification and assessment of potential vulnerabilities that could threaten the resilience of the future European power system. An overview of definitions and concepts related to resilience and vulnerability is given in Section 4.1. The assessment has been carried out in a two-stage approach with 1) an initial, broad, qualitative study of potential vulnerabilities in a future hybrid AC-DC grid with SF₆-free switchgear technology described in Section 4.2, followed by 2) a more narrow quantitative study of selected vulnerabilities identified in the qualitative assessment, as described in Section 4.3. First, however, an overview of the two-stage assessments and the main findings are given in the next two paragraphs.

The qualitative study focusses on the aspects of resilience most closely related to the MISSION technologies but also gives a broad, high-level overview of other aspects. To summarize the study, no new or increased vulnerabilities were revealed specifically associated with the new switchgear technologies developed in the MISSION project. The study did however give new insights into relevant vulnerabilities associated with new technology in general and vulnerabilities that will be influenced by factors related to the ongoing transition of the power system to low carbon solutions, such as vendor availability and TSO experience with new technology. Based on these assessments, some measures are recommended to ensure power system resilience as: close collaboration between vendors and TSOs in the design of new components; standardization of components and training on procedures for maintenance etc.; supporting development of HVDC circuit breaker technology; design HVDC grids with high selectivity or limited extent of meshing.

For the quantitative study, the choice was made to focus on the replacement of existing 420 kV HVAC circuit breakers based on SF₆ with corresponding circuit breakers based on new SF₆-free technology. The qualitative study gave no basis for expecting that the reliability of new switchgear technology on a component level in the long run will be different from that of the existing technology. Therefore, the quantitative study was framed as a “what if” analysis, illustrating with a simple simulation example how potential reductions in switchgear reliability *might* impact reliability and resilience on a power system level. Such reductions in component-level reliability might in principle occur due to lack of experience in manufacturing (vendor) and preventively maintaining (TSOs) the components. However, even with “worst-case” assumptions for the reliability of new SF₆-free switchgear technology, the decrease in system-level reliability and resilience for this simple example was found to be around 5%. For more realistic power grids it is likely that the change will be even smaller. Still, the simulation example illustrates the important role circuit breakers have in clearing faults and protecting the rest of the power system.

4.1 Definitions and frameworks for power system vulnerability and resilience

There are many ways to define and understand the concepts of vulnerability and resilience in the context of power systems. Following [27], power system resilience is “the ability to limit the extent, severity, and duration of system degradation following an extreme event”. Following [28], high vulnerability implies low resilience, and vice versa. This is illustrated on the right-hand side of Figure 4-1.

Vulnerability can furthermore be understood through the left-hand side of Figure 4-1, which is based on the conceptual bow-tie model often used in risk analysis [28]. In the middle of the bow-tie is a contingency involving one or more power system failures. The vulnerability of the power system is determined by its *susceptibility* to threats that can cause a contingency and by its *coping capacity*, i.e. how capable the power system is of coping with contingencies after they occur and limit their consequences. The figure also illustrates barriers that either can prevent a contingency from taking place or protect against its consequences. A vulnerability can be associated with a barrier that is either missing, weak or malfunctioning [28].

Resilience and vulnerability are most closely associated with events with critical consequences for the end-users of the power system due to large-scale and/or long-lasting power supply interruptions (blackouts). This is illustrated on the right-hand side of Figure 4-1, where these critical or extreme events are plotted as pink dots in a consequence diagram. Such blackouts can occur through a myriad of different mechanisms and barrier failures, often in combinations, and often as a sequence of cascading events. Some examples of mechanisms involved are hidden failures in fault clearance systems and unanticipated tripping of generator units.

Figure 4-1. Left-hand side: Bow tie model used in the power system vulnerability framework (top, based on (4)) and schematic progression of system state degradation for power supply interruption event with critical consequences (“resilience trapezoid”, below). Right-hand side: Events with critical consequences plotted in a consequence diagram.

The bow-tie model in Figure 4-1 is part of an existing conceptual framework for classifying and characterizing power system vulnerabilities. This framework has been developed together with an associated methodology for power system vulnerability assessment. This framework and methodology with previous applications is described in detail in [28]. Different qualitative and quantitative methods can be employed as part of the general vulnerability assessment methodology. In the present work, in-depth interview study was chosen as the method for the first, qualitative stage of the vulnerability assessment described in Section 4.2. In the subsequent quantitative assessment described in Section 4.3, a power system reliability and resilience analysis method was chosen that focus on fault clearance as a barrier to limit consequences of failures. The analysis investigates the implications of failures of the circuit breakers that are part of the fault clearance barrier.

4.2 Qualitative assessment of resilience and vulnerability

The qualitative vulnerability assessment methodology used in this study takes potential critical consequences as a starting point and works its way from the right-hand side to the left-hand side of the bow-tie model in a step-wise manner. The general steps are as follows:

1. Identify critical consequences
2. Identify critical contingencies potentially leading to critical consequences
3. Identify threats that can cause the critical contingencies
4. Identify vulnerabilities associated with the system's susceptibility and coping capacity
5. Identify factors influencing the power system's coping capacity
6. Identify existing and missing barriers against critical contingencies

The vulnerability assessment methodology used in this study has previously been applied to different power systems with different scale and scope with regards to geography, grid levels and issues of interest. Since the study considers possible future power systems and not a concrete system that is currently existing, it is challenging to pinpoint specific vulnerabilities associated with specific components or parts of the system. We therefore aim to identify more general types of vulnerabilities associated with types of outage or failure events rather than the outages of specific components. Compared to previous applications of the framework and methodology for vulnerability assessment, it is extended with an emphasis on the role of switchgear in the power grid as well as a method for quantifying the implications from a grid perspective of different ways that circuit breakers can fail.

4.2.1 Design of interview study to inform the vulnerability assessment

The six-step assessment methodology was used as a starting point in the in-depth interview study. The respondents included experts from eight major actors in the European electricity industry, including four TSOs, three vendors of switchgear and power converters (technology providers and manufacturers), and one offshore grid EPCI (Engineering, Procurement, Construction and Installation) supplier. These actors included industry partners in the MISSION consortium but also a few actors outside the MISSION consortium. One to three representatives from each company were present in the interviews, representing different perspectives, roles, domains and areas of expertise within the electric power engineering field.

The interviews started out with giving context to the study and trying to instill in the respondents a forward-looking mindset, stressing the importance of thinking beyond historical experiences and events. A semi-structured interview method was used, and the meeting structure was kept relatively open to avoid too narrow framing of the problem and to better leverage the expertise of the respondents. The respondents were interviewed during autumn 2024, and the raw notes from the interviews were kept confidentially with the authors and then aggregated and anonymized. These aggregated findings were presented to project partners and discussed in a workshop in January 2025 to validate the results from the study.

Superconducting systems were not considered in the interview study. The results from the vulnerability assessment were therefore supplemented by results from a Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA). The details of this analysis can be found in Appendix C (Chapter 9.3).

4.2.2 Overview of results of qualitative resilience/vulnerability assessment

This section presents the findings, mapped to the vulnerability framework, to give a systematic overview of potential vulnerabilities. The findings for each of the six steps of the methodology are summarized in Table 10, and broadly categorized into 1) the aspects associated with the traditional onshore grid and 2) additional aspects due to the introduction of an offshore grid. For both categories, the main emphasis is on aspects related to HV switchgear technologies, since these are expected to have the greatest influence on the resilience of the future European power system. The main findings are elaborated and discussed in the subsequent subsections.

Table 10: Summary of findings for each of the steps of the vulnerability assessment methodology.

Step of analysis	For onshore grid	In addition for offshore grid
1. Identify critical consequences	Loss of load supplied by a major (onshore) transmission substation	Load shedding due to lost power infeed from offshore HVDC grid higher than dimensioning incident (e.g. 1.4 GW in Nordic synchronous area)
2. Identify critical contingencies , that can lead to critical consequences	Busbar failures Multiple-outage contingencies due to circuit breakers failing to trip on command Outages while other components are being repaired/replaced	Common cause failures in bipolar HVDC cable systems Software failures of HVDC converters Destruction of offshore platforms (converter stations)
3. Identify threats that can lead to critical contingencies	Sabotage, terrorism, cyber threats Human errors (especially related to technology which operators have little experience on) High/low outside temperatures	Ship collisions Shipping activity (anchors) Extreme waves Earthquakes
4. Identify vulnerabilities related to the susceptibility and coping capacity of the power system	Series defects for components from the same vendor or based on same technology Component repair and replacement being reliant on a single vendor Smaller number of compatible spare components Reduced quality of preventive and corrective maintenance due to multiple switchgear technologies in the system	Limited selectivity of HVDC protection systems Faster dynamics and more challenging (corrective) control Insufficient fault ride through and overload capabilities of converters Remoteness and lack of spare capacity of offshore substations
5. Identify vulnerability-influencing factors	Lack of standardization TSOs' spare part strategy and vendor strategy Uncertain development of available vendors and their production capacity for SF ₆ -free HVAC breakers Roll-out strategy for SF ₆ -free switchgear Demand for expanding grid capacity (new grid components)	Uncertain development of HVDC circuit breaker technology and available vendors Communication system for HVDC protection systems Weather offshore Repair personnel missing offshore experience
6. Identify existing and missing barriers – measures to improve resilience	Close collaboration between TSOs and vendors in the development and testing of new technology Ensuring that multiple vendors will be available to supply similar technology/components	Utilize controllability of DC converters for corrective and restorative measures Remote control of offshore substations

	<p>Standardization of components and training on procedures for maintenance etc.</p> <p>Having more spares available (and prioritizing components as spares over components for grid expansion)</p> <p>Condition monitoring of individual components</p>	<p>Supporting/ensuring development of DC circuit breaker technology</p> <p>High selectivity of protection systems HVDC grids / Limiting the extent of meshed DC grids</p>
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4.2.3 Critical consequences

The vulnerability assessment methodology starts with identifying what the respondents consider a critical consequence. One type of event that most TSOs mentioned was the dimensioning incident (or dimensioning fault) for their synchronous system. This implies the loss of power injection to the system at the threshold that the system is expected to cope with before the frequency drop leads to large-scale under-frequency load shedding [29]. This extent of interruption of end-users' power supply was considered a critical consequence. The loss of infeed thresholds for the dimensioning incident in the Nordic and the Continental Europe synchronous areas currently are at 1.4 GW and 3 GW, respectively.

For considering the potential vulnerabilities of MVDC circuit breakers, one needs to consider consequences that are critical in the context of a local, MV scale, rather than the transnational transmission grid scale considered above. An example of a critical consequence in the context of MVDC breakers could be long-lasting power supply interruption at a data centre or some other industrial facility supplied by a DC distribution grid.

4.2.4 Critical contingencies

The types of critical contingencies that could constitute a dimensioning incident that were discussed in the interviews fall in two categories: 1) contingencies in the onshore HVAC power system that are "traditional" in the sense that they could occur in the existing power system and 2) new types of contingencies associated with the coupling with an offshore and predominantly HVDC-based power system. One example of the latter is the outage of an offshore grid feeding more than 1.4 GW offshore wind power production into the Nordic synchronous area. Figure 4-2 illustrates some simple cases of the couplings of offshore (HVDC) grid integrating offshore wind power into an onshore (HVAC) grid.

Figure 4-2. Schematic illustration of possible couplings of onshore (AC) and offshore (DC) power system through different types of switchgear technologies.

We first assume that the two offshore-onshore DC links are radially operated (possible for cases 2 and 3 of Figure 4-2) and feeding 2 GW wind power production each into the onshore grid. If they are monopole links, then any single cable or converter outage for the links would be a critical contingency for the Nordic synchronous area. If they are bipole links with metallic return, then a single HVDC cable or converter outage causes the unavailability of only 1 GW of the power capacity of the link. A critical contingency for such a bipole link would require a common-cause failure causing outage of both poles. This could result from failures of components on the AC-side or converter failure when only one converter is earthed, but these would be latent faults (manufacturer defect or design faults).

If the two DC links in Figure 4-2 are operated as a meshed DC grid, the consequences in the AC grid of a failure in the DC grid will depend on the power capacity and the actual power flow of the DC links, and how fast the available power capacity of the DC grid is restored following a failure [30]. This in turn depends on the number, location and type of switchgear that is used in the DC grid and the AC grid. With fewer switchgear in the DC grid, the selectivity of the protection system for the DC grid will be reduced. With no selectivity (case 1 in Figure 4-2), a failure on the DC side could be a critical contingency. A case with partial selectivity is shown in case 2 in Figure 4-2. With full selectivity (case 3 in Figure 4-2), a critical contingency could still occur in case DC breakers fail to trip on command or due to unwanted non-selective tripping of circuit breakers.

For MVDC grids, an example of a critical contingency could involve a breaker not able to interrupt the fault current from a primary fault, leading to explosions and fire and a long outage duration. If the system is fully redundant, it would take a second fault during this outage duration to cause power supply interruptions at the facility.

4.2.5 Vulnerabilities related to the power system's susceptibility to threats

Several of the relevant threats (see Table 1) are the same as in the past, but existing barriers to manage these threats for existing technologies may not be sufficient for new technologies. Several of the identified vulnerabilities were also flagged as common reliability concerns using current technology. Some TSOs had concerns about insufficient training and experience with new technologies, which may reduce the quality of preventive maintenance to avoid failures. The present study only identified a few differences between existing and new technologies that might lead to different failure mechanisms:

- 1) SF₆-free HVAC circuit breakers based on vacuum technology have two pressure vessels (the vacuum chamber for the current interruption and the surrounding high-pressure gas chamber for providing electric insulation), while SF₆-based circuit breakers have only one. Still, the expectation is that the reliability of the switchgear is not going to change significantly. One argument for expecting that new SF₆-free HVAC circuit breakers will have the same reliability as existing SF₆-based circuit breakers is that new technologies are expected to pass the same type tests as existing technologies. However, type tests are limited to cover the most important requirements of a functioning circuit breaker over a limited time, and they will not uncover the effects of ageing and may not uncover all design and production defects.
- 2) New HV and MV DC switchgear and circuit breakers that are being developed have often more electronics and more parts than corresponding AC circuit breakers and may therefore have lower

reliability. The MVDC circuit breaker architecture proposed in MISSION is less reliant on active power semiconductors. On the other hand, the proposed DC breaker architecture involves some complexity in the coordination of the parts: The continuous current conduction path is combined with the switching section, which is needed to force the current to zero and toward energy dissipating elements. The very high speed required to switch the current is one of the main advantages of the proposed technology, while it implies some mechanical and breaking complexity compared to other DC breaker architectures. DC circuit breakers should be capable of operating very fast because in a DC network the fault current tend to increase rapidly and the fault energy should be immediately limited once the fault occurs.

Another more general concern was that similar technologies could all suffer from the same design flaw and that this could lead to series defects. This vulnerability is related to technology development in general, where first-generation products may have some defects that are corrected in second-generation products some years later. The likelihood of this vulnerability could be higher for the development of SF₆-free technologies than otherwise because the F-Gas regulation may compress the timeline for development. Although there is limited operational experience with the new technologies, there is currently no basis for expecting that they are more susceptible to threats and thus more likely to fail.

For Superconducting Cable Systems (SCS), it is critical to maintain the cryogen temperature at or below a given temperature limit to ensure reliable operation. For the SCS considered as part of this work, higher temperatures than 77 K can cause hotspots in the HTS conductors and lead to quenching, resulting in transmission loss. This is managed using cryostats, advanced insulation, vacuum pumping, and Cooling and Pumping Stations (CPS) that periodically remove, recool, and repressurise the cryogen. LN₂ Breakout Joints facilitate this process by allowing both current flow—via bonded HTS tapes and copper connections—and LN₂ extraction. Failures in these joints can lead to electrical arcing or coolant loss through leaks or pressure drops. More details can be found in Appendix C (Chapter 9.3), gives a summary of a failure mode and effect analysis (FMEA) for SCS.

4.2.6 Vulnerabilities related to the power system's coping capacity

The coping capacity of the power system depends on barriers such as grid component redundancy and corrective measures that limit the extent and severity of system degradation after failures. Corrective measures include the operation of the *fault clearance system (FCS)*, which is comprised of the protection system in addition to the circuit breakers. The parts of an FCS are illustrated in Figure 4-3. Failure of this barrier – for instance when a circuit breaker fails to trip on command after a fault has been identified – constitutes a vulnerability. If this happens, the backup operation of a nearby (secondary) FCS may lead to more components than necessary being taken out of service to clear a fault.

Figure 4-3. The parts of the fault clearance system (FCS), comprised by the protection system and the circuit breaker. Based on [31].

The coping capacity also depends on restorative actions to limit the duration of system degradation and restore system operation and power supply to end-users. In the current AC power system, there are typically no end-user consequences of individual failures of switchgear due to the level of redundancy and selectivity at both the substation level and power grid level. The same level of redundancy and selectivity is not expected in an offshore DC power grid due to high costs offshore and lack of available HVDC switchgear technology. Opinions differed among the respondents about when HVDC circuit breakers would be commercially available and a cost-efficient solution for offshore grids. Moreover, DC protection systems need to act faster than AC protection systems [15], leading to more stringent communication requirements, which is a factor that influences vulnerability.

After the system has reached a degraded state, restorative measures such as repairing or replacing faulty components may be needed to restore system operation. Several vulnerabilities related to long repair times of switchgear were highlighted in the study, associated with 1) technician experience, 2) availability of spares on site, and 3) availability of spares on a national or European level.

The first vulnerability was reflected by the concern some TSOs had with insufficient training and experience with managing and repairing different technologies. For HVAC circuit breakers, they currently have experience only with SF₆-based technology, but during the transition to an SF₆-free power system they will be required to have experience with one or two new technologies in addition. Lack of standardisation for new technologies could mean that TSOs become dependent on vendors for fault diagnosis and repair/replacement. Vendors on the other hand state that there are strong similarities in operation and asset management between different SF₆-based and SF₆-free technologies.

Another factor influencing the coping capacity was the experience that repair personnel had with working offshore. For offshore substations (platforms), the restoration time is typically longer because of the remote and usually unmanned locations. The restoration time depends on the weather and on the extent of redundancy and spares available on offshore platforms. The extent of redundancy and spares are in turn influenced by costs and available space on the offshore platforms.

The third factor that could influence the coping capacity related to repairing and replacing switchgear after failures was the availability of vendors and their priorities. For new technologies, there was uncertainty about how many vendors would be supplying compatible technologies in the future and concern about a “lock-in” effect where a TSO becomes too reliant on a single vendor. Another potential vulnerability is that the vendor(s) might lack the capacity to produce new components since they are only gradually increasing production capacity when the demand for new components is uncertain. This is influenced by regulations and politics, translating into demand by new components for grid expansion projects and/or for replacing e.g. SF₆-based switchgear. TSOs’ strategies for grid development and for phasing out SF₆ are therefore vulnerability-influencing factors. Scenarios and strategies for the phase-out of SF₆ were described in Section 3, and strategies will be investigated in more detail in subsequent tasks in MISSION WP1. There was also concern that vendors might prioritize producing new components for grid expansion over repairing faulty components. TSO experience shows repair times of a few months on current technology where several vendors compete, which could delay more if only one vendor is available for new technologies. On the other hand, for components with old technology that is no longer being installed, the vulnerability is that a TSO’s spare inventory may be running low before the technology is entirely phased out.

4.2.7 Measures to improve resilience

Strengthening existing barriers or implementing new barriers are measures to improve the resilience of the power system. The last step of the vulnerability assessment methodology is to identify existing and missing barriers against critical contingencies to reduce their likelihood and consequence. Some of the barriers related to switchgear technology are discussed below.

A preventive measure that will reduce the susceptibility to failures is to improve the monitoring and self-diagnostics systems of new components which may potentially have new failure mechanisms. Collaboration between TSOs and vendors in the development and testing of new technology reduces the likelihood of design flaws and series defects. There is a need to manage relationships between these actors in a different way than in the past, and some steps in this direction have already been taken [32]. Sharing experiences after product release and providing good documentation on the function and failure of components will improve preventive maintenance by the TSOs and reduce the likelihood of failures.

Designing the coupled offshore/onshore grid with switchgear mostly in onshore substations reduces the cost compared to offshore. Such a solution makes it more economically feasible to ensure selectivity and reduce the time to restore the operation of the DC grid after failures. This improves the short-term coping capacity but is also a measure to reduce repair time because it improves the availability of spares and personnel.

To reduce the repair/replacement time of faulty circuit breakers and thus improve coping capacity, vendors could prioritize to assign more of their capacity to providing fast repair service. The longer-term coping capacity related to availability and production capacity of vendors is also important to improve but requires measures to improve supply chain resilience that is outside the scope of this study.

4.3 Quantitative assessment of grid resilience and reliability

The qualitative assessment summarized above revealed no new or increased vulnerabilities specifically associated with the new switchgear technologies developed in the MISSION project. Moreover, there are no relevant reliability statistics for new switchgear technologies, and bottom-up estimation of future failure rates of new technologies (e.g. through detailed FMECA analyses) are outside the scope of MISSION WP1. Attempts on precise, quantitative predictions of the risk with respect to grid reliability associated with replacing existing switchgear technology with new technologies will therefore have limited value. Instead, this section will present a quantitative illustration of how potential changes in switchgear reliability *might* impact reliability and resilience on a power system level. This sensitivity analysis or “what-if” analysis will focus on 420 kV AC circuit breakers.

4.3.1 The relationship between circuit breaker reliability and power system reliability

The reliability and resilience of a power grid depends on the reliability of its components and the role or importance of these components in supplying end-users with electricity. For circuit breakers, the impact of component reliability on grid-level reliability has been very limited because of redundancy at both the substation level and at the power grid level. In other words, circuit breaker failures rarely lead to interruption of power supply to end-users [33]. In principle, this relationship can be inferred by statistics. However, this is only valid for a given, existing (historical) system and only if sufficiently detailed information has been reported by the system operator both for component-level reliability and grid-level reliability. Section 4.3.3 will give an overview of the somewhat limited information that is publicly available.

For a future power grid, the impact of changes in the reliability of grid components can be modelled using the methods of power system reliability analysis. Figure 4-4 gives a conceptual illustration of how such an analysis captures this relationship: given a power grid model and information about the reliability of power grid components (in addition to other inputs), it simulates failures of these components and the power supply interruptions at one or more load points that may result from these failures. The outputs of such an analysis are traditionally reliability of supply indicators such as the expected energy not supplied (ENS) during interruption events. These indicators give information about the grid-level reliability. More background on power system reliability analysis methods is given in Section 4.3.2.

Figure 4-4. Illustration of power system reliability analysis and the simulation of an exemplary failure event.

In Figure 4-4 an example of a single-component contingency is illustrated. The component in this example is a transmission line. The fault clearing systems (FCSs), comprising protection systems and circuit breakers, are depicted as squares. In the example, the primary FCS operates successfully, and only the one faulty component is taken out of service. This contingency leads to power supply interruption for end-users under the load points on the lower-right bus in Figure 4-4. However, in real power grids, the great majority of failures on the transmission grid level do not lead to any consequences for end-users. In fact, transmission systems are traditionally planned and operated according to the N-1 criterion, which requires that the system should withstand any single-component contingency without consequences for end-users.

Figure 4-5 and Figure 4-6 illustrate two other failure events that are associated with the fault clearance system and that involve two different failure mechanisms A and B:

- A. Figure 4-5 illustrates a failure mechanism that leads to the circuit breaker *tripping without a command*. This failure is defined as having a failure rate λ^{CB} .
- B. Figure 4-6 illustrates a failure mechanism that leads to the circuit breaker *failing to trip* on command. This event is driven by the conditional probability of missing operation p_m of the line's primary FCS circuit breakers.

While failure mechanism A leads to single-component outage, failure mechanism B requires a nearby backup protection system to operate to clear the fault, which results in a multiple-component contingency. In the simple example in Figure 4-6, the resulting system state is one where the lower-right bus bar (primary substation) is isolated from the rest of the system, resulting in extensive power supply interruptions for the connected load point.

Figure 4-5. Failure mechanisms that lead to the HVCB tripping without a command (failure rate λ^{CB}).

Figure 4-6. Failure mechanisms that lead to the HVCB failing to trip on command (probability p_m).

4.3.2 Methods of grid reliability and grid resilience analysis

The quantitative assessment in MISSION aims to give insight into potential *grid resilience* impacts as well as *grid reliability* impacts. Grid resilience is most closely associated with rare events with critical consequences, such as extensive, system-wide power supply interruptions (blackouts). Grid reliability, on the other hand, is often determined by all the less severe and more frequent power supply interruption events. Traditional methods for power system reliability analysis are suitable for capturing the relatively frequent kinds of events relevant for grid reliability but may fail to capture events with critical consequences more relevant for grid resilience [28].

Figure 4-7 gives a conceptual illustration of the distinction between grid reliability and grid resilience analysis. Both types of analyses aim to capture a subset of potential power supply interruption events most relevant for the analysis: grid reliability analysis is most concerned with relatively frequent events, while grid resilience analysis is most concerned with rare and critical events. More frequent interruption events give higher contributions to indicators such as the expected energy not supplied during a year, while the contribution of critical events to the expected value is often negligible due to their very low probabilities. However, the probability of critical events may be higher than estimated in traditional reliability analysis methods. For instance, the probability of multiple-component contingencies will be underestimated if one neglects relevant dependent events, such as the possibility of fault clearance system misoperation.

Figure 4-7. The distinction between grid reliability analysis and grid resilience analysis

For the purpose of the grid resilience analysis in MISSION, existing reliability analysis methods [31, 34, 35] that are capturing fault clearance system misoperation have been extended to also be applicable to resilience analysis. The details of the methodology can be found in Appendix 9, but in brief, the main principle is that it simulates both primary (initial) component failures, subsequent fault clearance system misoperation, and subsequent independent component failures. The results are being post-processed so that they can be presented both from the traditional grid reliability perspective and from the grid resilience perspective.

4.3.3 Statistical basis on HVCB reliability and power system reliability

This section will summarize information available from publicly available circuit breaker fault statistics and reliability of supply statistics. This will be used to explain how available information is insufficient for statistical inference or precise prediction of the grid reliability impact of new circuit breaker technologies. However, some input data assumptions for the quantitative reliability and resilience assessment will nevertheless be suggested.

For information on circuit breaker reliability on the component level, the most detailed information can be found in the fault statistics collected and published by CIGRE [36]. These statistics have an international coverage, and they indicate that circuit breaker reliability varies strongly between different countries. Since the data are anonymized and not linked to specific countries, it is not a suitable data source for estimates of the reliability of components in a specific country or region, such as Europe. Neither do the CIGRE statistics include information necessary to relate component reliability to the power system reliability for a given country.

There is even less information available on the reliability of components based on new technologies, such as 420 kV SF₆-free HVAC circuit breakers. One reason is simply that there is not enough operational experience to have reliability statistics that can be used in a meaningful way. Statistics for circuit breakers designed for lower voltage levels are not representative for 420 kV applications. MISSION will, however, contribute to increasing the amount of operational experience by piloting the operation of two SF₆-free 420 kV circuit breakers. After the pilot phase, one will have a little more information about the behaviour and reliability performance of the new technology, although it is still not enough to provide reliable statistics.

For information on reliability on a power grid level in Europe, some information is made available by ENTSO-E and by individual European TSOs. Most details can be found for the Nordic and Baltic countries, some of which have been publishing annual grid disturbance reports for decades [37]. These reports give information about reliability of supply indicators such as annual energy not supplied (ENS). The statistics focus on disturbances due to failures of grid components at voltage levels 100 kV and above. Table 11 shows the annual ENS contributions from different grid levels for all the countries averaged over the years 2014–2023. To give some context, the total consumption of these countries is around 450 TWh per year. This means that around 0.00005% of the total annual energy demand in the countries was not supplied to end-users due to failures at voltage levels 380–420 kV

Table 11: Annual average energy not supplied in Baltic and Nordic countries for 2014–2023 by voltage level [38].

Voltage level	ENS (MWh)
100–150 kV	2398.3
220–330 kV	776.6
380–420 kV	235.0

The ENTSO-E grid disturbance statistics for Nordic and Baltic countries also contain information about the contribution to ENS from different component types. In the period 2014–2023, the median share of ENS due to circuit breaker faults for these countries was around 5%, while the corresponding number for protection and control system was around 22%. These statistics are reproduced in Appendix C.

The number of component faults that lead to energy not supplied is relatively small. In 2014–2023 there were on average about 1800 faults reported per year on components at 100 kV and above in the Nordic and Baltic countries, and of these about 450 faults per year that caused ENS. Note that these statistics do not differentiate by voltage level or component type. It is likely that the share of faults leading to ENS was even smaller if one considered only the highest voltage levels. Such information is available for Norway [33], where less than 6% of the disturbances at the 420 kV transmission grid level caused energy not supplied in the period 2009-2018.

None of these statistics give information about the failure mechanisms or failure modes of FCSs. Two sources were used as reference data, [39] for CB and [31] for the protection system. Based on recent outage data during 2012-2021 from Svenska kraftnät, [39] defined a reference data set for CBs. In [31], based on an analysis of data from Statnett, a reference data set for protection system failures was defined. This reference data set is summarized in Table 12. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, no similar analysis has been carried out more recently. This data set was subsequently used in a series of studies of the impact of protection and control system failures on power system reliability, as reported in [34].

Table 12: Reference data for fault clearance system reliability [31, 34, 39]

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
Protection system failure rate	λ^{PS}	0.025	failures/year
Circuit breaker failure rate	λ^{CB}	0.0081	failures/year
Protection system repair time	r^{PS}	2.0	hours/failure
Circuit breaker repair time	r^{CB}	19.81	hours/failure
Switching time	s^{CB}	0.5	hours/action
Probability of missing operation	p_m^{FCS}	0.0205	probability
Probability of unwanted, non-selective operation	p_{ns}^{FCS}	0.0070	probability

These data include the failure mechanism illustrated in Figure 4-6, characterized by the failure rates λ^{PS} and λ^{CB} of unwanted spontaneous tripping of the protection systems and CBs of a fault clearance system unit, and the associated repair times r^{PS} and r^{CB} of the protection systems and CBs. (MISSION TSO partner experience indicate somewhat higher values of λ^{CB} and r^{CB} than given by [39].)

The data in [31] also include the failure mechanism illustrated in Figure 4-6, characterized by the probability p_m^{FCS} of missing operation of the primary fault clearance system in case of failure of a power system unit, causing the activation of the secondary/back-up fault clearance system. A power system unit is a group of components which are delimited by one or more circuit breakers [40]. The probability p_{ns}^{FCS} characterizes another fault clearance failure mechanism that does not depend on circuit breaker reliability, namely unwanted non-selective tripping of a power system unit's secondary/back-up fault clearance system, even if the failure was correctly cleared by the primary fault clearance system. The time interval s^{CB} is the switching time to re-close a CB tripped due to a missing (backup reaction) or non-selective operation.

4.3.4 Case definition for numerical simulation example

This section defines the “what-if” analysis (sensitivity analysis) that will illustrate how potential changes in the component-level reliability for HVAC circuit breakers might impact reliability and resilience on a power grid level. It will consider the information in Section 4.3.3 to define cases to be simulated using methods outlined in Section 4.3.2. As described in the qualitative assessment, there is no basis for expecting that component level reliability will significantly change from that of the existing technology. The purpose of the analysis is to nevertheless ask the question: What if it did turn out that the component reliability is reduced for the new technology, how much of a reduction would it take to give a noticeable worsening of grid reliability?

In mathematical terms, this is a sensitivity analysis considering the following relation:

$$\lambda_0 \rightarrow \lambda = \lambda_0 + \Delta\lambda \Rightarrow$$

$$EENS_0 \rightarrow EENS = EENS_0 + \Delta EENS.$$

Here, subscript 0 denotes the current situation with existing technology, $\Delta\lambda$ denotes the difference in reliability between existing and new technology, and $\Delta EENS$ denotes the consequent change in grid

reliability (for example measured as the estimated average annual energy not supplied, denoted Expected Energy Not Supplied). All else being equal, $\Delta\lambda = 0$ implies $\Delta EENS = 0$.

Based on the qualitative assessment in Sec. 4.2, the following potential vulnerabilities are selected for this quantitative analysis:

1. Failure probabilities for the new technology could be higher due to lack of experience in manufacturing (by vendors) and preventively maintaining (by TSOs) the components, or due to series defects (undetected vulnerabilities in the component design).
2. Repair times become longer due to lack of experience with new technology and the strain on maintenance organizations. TSOs with internal maintenance teams needing competence on several technologies during the transition to fully SF₆-free components and TSOs relying on supplier maintenance may experience a “lock-in” effect on a single supplier, delaying repairs.

Vulnerability 1 would give an effect that comes in addition to the traditional “bathtub curve”, which describes the initially higher and decreasing failure rates for new components, which could occur for old as well as new technology. However, failure rates could also be higher for first generation components the first few years if they are based on a new technology, before learning effects improve the reliability for subsequent generations. A fast adoption rate of the technology could accelerate the learning effect.

To have some baseline assumptions for the reliability of existing circuit breaker technology, the reference data set for fault clearance system reliability [31, 34, 39] is used. Since there is no information to distinguish between the share of failures attributed to the circuit breakers themselves and the share of protection and control system failures, some additional assumptions must be made. Based on information in the ENTSO-E statistics [38] and the Statnett statistics for Norway [33], it is assumed that the contributions to failure probabilities for missing operation p_m and unwanted non-selective operation p_{ns} is as stated in Table 13.

Table 13: Assumptions about how large share of fault clearance system misoperation can be associated with the circuit breaker and the protection system, respectively.

Parameter	Circuit breaker (CB)	Protection and control system (PS)
p_m	25%	75%
p_{ns}	0%	100%

Here, the probability of missing operation, $p_m^{FCS} = p_m^{PS} + p_m^{CB}$, has the majority of its contributions from protection and control system failures. It is moreover assumed that the unwanted non-selective operation failure type does not depend on circuit breakers themselves but are fully attributed to the protection and control system [41]. Further, the effective failure rate and repair time for the FCS is found by

$$\lambda^{FCS} = \lambda^{PS} + \lambda^{CB} = 0.0331 \text{ failures/year}$$

$$r^{FCS} = (r^{PS} \cdot \lambda^{PS} + r^{CB} \cdot \lambda^{CB}) / (\lambda^{PS} + \lambda^{CB}) = 6.36 \text{ hours/failure}$$

The resulting baseline reliability parameters for the numerical simulation example are given in Table 14. The example considers the reliability of overhead lines and fault clearance system for these overhead lines. The reliability data used for 400 kV overhead transmission lines can be found in [39]. Circuit breakers for capacitor banks and shunt reactors are not considered, and it is assumed that all circuit breakers are 420 kV air-insulated switchgear (AIS). Busbars are considered 100 percent reliable and are thus left out.

Table 14: Reliability parameters used for the numerical simulation example.

Description	Symbol	Value	Unit
<u>Fault clearance system:</u>			
Failure rate	λ^{FCS}	0.0331	failures/year
Repair time	r^{FCS}	6.36	hours/failure
Switching time	s^{CB}	0.5	hours/action
Probability of missing operation due to protection system	p_m^{PS}	0.0154	(probability)
Probability of missing operation due to circuit breaker	p_m^{CB}	0.0051	(probability)
Probability of unwanted, non-selective operation	p_{ns}^{FCS}	0.0070	(probability)
<u>Overhead lines:</u>			
Failure rate	λ^l	0.0034	failures/km/year
Repair time	r^l	4.14	hours/failure

For the purpose of quantitatively illustrating the impact on reliability on a power system level, a small 400 kV test system was chosen. The system specifications are based on a well-known test system originally developed for economic studies [42]. The system specifications are given in Appendix C.

The numerical example will consider as a baseline the present grid with existing SF₆-based HVAC circuit breakers. This will be denoted Case 0 and has component reliability parameters as given in Table 14. All components of the same type are assumed to have the same reliability parameter values.

The baseline grid reliability results for Case 0 will be compared with results for a future grid. For simplicity and to show the trends more clearly, all existing SF₆-based HVAC circuit breakers in this future grid are assumed to have been replaced by new SF₆-free circuit breakers at the stage that is considered. This corresponds to a scenario for the future grid where the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy of Section 3 has been followed. These new SF₆-free circuit breakers in the test system could be based on different technologies, either vacuum or alternative gases to SF₆. Assuming that the reliability of these new circuit breakers is the same as those in the present grid, and assuming all else equal, also the grid reliability will be the same as for Case 0. If we instead ask "what if" the circuit breaker reliability parameters were different for the future grid, we can estimate the potential impact this would have on grid reliability. Table 15 defines three such sensitivity analysis cases: Case A considers an increase in the failure rate for circuit breakers tripping without a command, Case B considers an increase in the time to repair or replace circuit breakers after such failures, and Case C considers an increase in the probability of missing operation of the circuit breaker. This analysis is a simple local and "one at a time" sensitivity analysis that isolates that effect component reliability parameter has on the grid-level

reliability. For each of the reliability parameters, an increase of 30% is assumed to test a pessimistic “worst case”.

Table 15: Sensitivity cases for assessing impact of circuit breakers on grid reliability and resilience. The values show differences in reliability parameter values compared to Case 0.

Parameter	Case 0	Case A	Case B	Case C
Protections system failure rate λ^{PS}	-	-	-	-
Circuit breaker failure rate λ^{CB}	-	+30%	-	-
Protection system repair time r^{PS}	-	-	-	-
Circuit breaker repair time r^{CB}	-	-	+30%	-
Switching time s^{CB}	-	-	-	-
Probability of protection system missing operation p_m^{PS}	-	-	-	-
Probability of circuit breaker missing operation p_m^{CB}	-	-	-	+30%
Probability of unwanted, non-selective operation p_{ns}^{FCS}	-	-	-	-

4.3.5 Grid reliability results for numerical simulation example

Figure 4-8 shows the grid reliability results for the numerical simulation example defined in the previous section. This presentation will focus on results for the expected annual energy not supplied (rightmost columns), but results are also shown for the expected annual frequency of power supply interruptions, the average duration of power supply interruptions, and the expected number of hours per year that power supply is unavailable. For Case A and B, there is no appreciable difference in the future grid reliability compared to the present grid reliability (Case 0). These two cases assume changes in reliability parameters related to the circuit breaker tripping without a command. This type of failure will by itself result in only one transmission line being in an outage state, and since the test system is N-1 secure, it takes at least an additional, independent failure to cause a power supply interruption. The probability of such overlapping outages is extremely low, and the contributions to the ENS estimates are smaller than the statistical uncertainty in the simulations.

Figure 4-8. Key power system reliability indicators for the test system calculated for the base case (0) and different sensitivity cases for (A–B).

For Case C, on the other hand, there is a small but appreciable increase in ENS in the future grid compared to the present grid (Case 0). The reason is that Case C involves an increase in the probability of missing operation, a type of circuit breaker failure that results in multiple transmission lines being in an outage state and thus a high likelihood of power supply interruptions. Still, the increase in ENS is less than 5.3%, which is much lower than the 30% increase assumed in the probability of missing operation.

4.3.6 Grid resilience results for the numerical simulation example

The grid reliability results in the previous subsection showed only a small impact on grid-level reliability of potential reductions in circuit breaker reliability. However, one could hypothesize that reduced circuit breaker reliability could have a large impact on grid resilience even if the impact on grid reliability is moderate. To test this hypothesis, Figure 4-9 shows the contributions to reliability indicators for different contingency depths, i.e., for sets of contingencies with different numbers of components being in an outage state. (Note log-scale on the y-axis of the two upper panels.) The contributions for larger contingency depths are associated with rarer events with higher consequences and thus give information about the resilience of the grid. Only a very small increase in the indicators can be seen when comparing Case C with Case 0. When comparing contingency of depth 5 (contingencies involving 5 power system units out of service) with contingencies involving only 1 power system unit, this increase is only marginally greater in relative terms. For this simulation example, these results thus contradict the hypothesis that reduced circuit breaker reliability significantly reduces grid resilience.

Figure 4-9. Results of grid resilience analysis showing reliability indicator contributions for different depth of contingencies.

4.3.7 Discussion of quantitative grid reliability and resilience results

The numerical simulation example has illustrated the kinds of impacts a reduction in HVAC circuit breaker reliability may have on the reliability and resilience of the power grid. In this example, the impacts were relatively modest even for rather pessimistic assumptions about the reliability of new circuit breaker technology.

The case defined for the numerical simulation example has many simplifications compared to real-world power grids. However, there are several reasons why more accurate cases and simulation methods can be expected to have an even lower impact on grid-level reliability:

- “Worst-case” reliability parameter values were chosen for the “what-if” analysis, and smaller reductions in circuit breaker reliability than this are more likely. This would lead to correspondingly smaller increases in energy not supplied than the “worst-case” estimates in the simulation example (around 5%).
- The scope of the analysis is limited to the 400 kV grid, and it does not consider failures at lower voltage levels. As described in Section 4.3.3, the majority of the energy not supplied can be attributed to failures at voltage levels below 380-420 kV. This contributes to making the 5% increase in ENS estimated in the simulation example an overestimate for the full power grid.
- The test system is assumed to have a single-bus single-breaker substation configuration for all the primary substations in the 400 kV grid. This is a pessimistic assumption, and even if substation configuration policies vary between European countries, real grids are likely to have higher redundancy at the substation level. For this reason, the simulation example is likely to overestimate the grid-level reliability impact of lower circuit breaker reliability.
- Since the test system is always N-1 secure, there are no contributions to energy not supplied for any single-component contingency. If there were periods of the year when the system were not N-1 secure, then there would also be contributions for single-component outages, and the relative contribution of contingencies due to missing FCS operation would be lower. As seen in previous studies [41], this is likely to reduce the relative impact of circuit breaker reliability on grid reliability.

Aside from potential changes in component reliability in the future power grid, there are many other changes from the present grid that are likely to change the reliability and resilience of the grid. One factor is that the grid is expected to be expanded significantly, as described in Section 2.1, which may increase the level of meshing and redundancy as well as the grid capacity. Another factor is the system loading level which depend on the connection of new load demand and generation. In some places and for some years, the system loading may increase at a greater pace than the expansion of the grid capacity. This would reduce the risk margins (e.g. given by the N-1 criterion) and the levels of redundancy. Such a development could have a greater impact on grid reliability than the changes in the circuit breaker reliability assumed in the example, where the loading level of the system was assumed constant.

The simulation example makes relatively simplistic assumptions about circuit breaker failure modes and mechanisms. For instance, one type of failure that is not considered is if the breaker opens but is unable to interrupt the current, which will cause major damage to the equipment and most likely longer repair or replacement times than assumed here. Moreover, for the failure modes that are explicitly included, there is a weak statistical basis for the reliability parameter assumptions. There is therefore a need for continuing the initiatives on collection and analysis of fault data that have been started by ENTSO-E and others, especially to be able to differentiate contributions from different fault clearance system failure modes.

The quantitative analysis above has illustrated the significance of circuit breaker reliability for the grid reliability and how this can be estimated. There are however two points that are not illustrated by the simulation example but that should nevertheless be stressed: 1) Circuit breakers have an important role as part of fault clearance systems in protecting other power grid components from further damage in case they fail. 2) If there were fewer circuit breakers in the grid, larger parts of the grid would need to be taken out of service in case of failure to avoid significant equipment damage, which would reduce the reliability of the grid. 3) The example only considered an onshore HVAC grid, but for HVDC grids, in particular offshore, the absence of switchgear to properly protect the system in case of faults may threaten the reliability and resilience of the grid of the future. This last point was also emphasized in Section 4.2 in the presentation of the qualitative vulnerability assessment.

4.3.8 Implications for implementation strategies for SF₆-free switchgear

The grid reliability and resilience assessment in the subsections above indicate that the technical risk associated with the new SF₆-free HVAC circuit breaker technology is at an acceptable level, even under quite pessimistic assumptions. A thorough assessment of strategies for managing this risk in the rollout and installation of new circuit breakers would therefore be of limited value in this report.

Nevertheless, given the uncertainties that are discussed, it is prudent to follow a precautionary approach when integrating new technologies into the grid. One natural part of the strategy is therefore to – where possible given other objectives and constraints – to first replace the SF₆-based circuit breakers in less critical locations in the grid. This way, even if failures do occur faster or more frequently than expected, the consequences in terms of end-user power supply interruptions will be relatively small. Component locations in a concrete power grid can be ranked according to criticality using power system reliability analysis methods such as those used for this report [43], [44].

In addition to location, the application of switchgear matters, and the technical requirements will be different for switchgear used for lines, capacitor banks and shunt reactors. For instance, shunt reactor circuit breakers will have more challenging operational conditions. These circuit breakers are therefore less suitable candidates for replacement for first-generation SF₆-free circuit breakers. Instead, one can reduce the risk by postponing replacement of these to more experience is gained and later generations of SF₆-free circuit breakers are ready to be installed.

Economic and environmental analyses will be carried out in Task 1.3 to provide an overall assessment of costs and impacts, which will also include the technical risk and resilience considerations documented in the present report. These analyses will include component-level life cycle assessments,

techno-economic evaluations, and scenario-based comparisons under “Business-as-usual” and “SF₆-free by 2050” scenarios. The results will inform the implementation strategies and recommendations to be developed in Task 1.4. This combination will provide a broad evidence-based foundation for informed decision-making, while highlighting the trade-offs between environmental impact, economic feasibility, and system reliability.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides the broader power system context for the subsequent work packages of the MISSION project, which focus primarily on component development and testing. It examines the ongoing transformation of the European power system driven by the energy transition and the imperative to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In particular, it addresses the need to migrate away from SF₆-based technologies by developing quantitative scenarios for the future circuit breaker (CB) population and assessing the implications of new switchgear technologies on system resilience.

Chapter 2 underscores that meeting the EU's 2050 climate targets will necessitate a substantial increase in renewable energy sources (RES), with wind and solar comprising the majority of new capacity. Distributed generation (DG) plays a critical role across all scenarios, requiring active consumer participation, high levels of self-consumption, and strong local integration of renewables. These developments demand a more flexible grid infrastructure and new operational paradigms to accommodate decentralized and weather-dependent generation. High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) technology is identified as a key enabler of long-distance power transfer and cross-border interconnectivity, potentially serving as the backbone of future transmission systems. Medium Voltage DC (MVDC) is also emerging as a promising solution for urban, offshore, and marine distribution-level applications.

Chapter 3 focuses on the future deployment of circuit breakers, projecting a 40–60% increase in the total AC CB population by 2050. Given the aging infrastructure currently in place, the number of CBs to be commissioned will surpass today's installed base, even under a business-as-usual replacement scenario. Two transition strategies were assessed: a gradual, age-based replacement ("Business as usual") and an accelerated transition to SF₆-free technology by 2050 ("SF₆-free by 2050"). An aggressive transition strategy to reach SF₆-free operation by 2050 ("SF₆-free by 2050") requires 10-50% more CBs by 2050, or up to 75% in the case when SF₆-free alternatives are delayed by 5 years, compared to the gradual exchange of circuit breakers as they age ("Business as usual"). This represents the main cost difference for these two strategies, assuming that a rapid replacement of circuit breakers is feasible for TSOs. The "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy reduces total emissions of SF₆ by almost 20% compared to the "Business as usual" strategy. The added emissions related to manufacturing and commissioning of more CBs have not been investigated, but this could potentially reduce the emissions savings. A 5-year delay in the availability of SF₆-free circuit breakers increases the total SF₆ emissions by 10% and 15% for "SF₆-free by 2050" and "Business as usual", respectively. However, both transitioning strategies reduce SF₆ emissions significantly compared to the continued use of SF₆. By 2050, the two strategies "Business as usual" and "SF₆-free by 2050" reduce emissions by 17% and 25%, respectively, compared to the continued use of SF₆. By 2100, those emission reductions have increased to 58% and 65%. The choice between the "Business as usual" strategy and the "SF₆-free by 2050" strategy is a matter of costs, regulatory frameworks and practical feasibility, as the latter strategy requires decommissioning and commissioning many more circuit breakers.

Chapter 4 presents a qualitative assessment of grid resilience considering new switchgear technologies. No evidence was found of new or increased vulnerabilities directly attributable to the SF₆-free technologies developed in the MISSION project. Nonetheless, the study identified broader

concerns, including vendor availability, limited TSO experience with new technologies, and the complexity of developing integrated onshore-offshore HVDC grids. In addition, comes the general concern for any new technology that first-generation products may have higher failure rates than later-generation products.

To mitigate these risks, the study recommends continuing to strengthen collaboration between TSOs and vendors during the development and testing of new technology, component standardization, structured training programs, prioritizing spare components and vendor repair capacity, and support for HVDC circuit breaker development. The qualitative assessment gave no basis for expecting that the reliability of new SF₆-free 420 kV HVAC circuit breakers technology will be lower than existing SF₆-based technology in the long term. Nevertheless, a quantitative “what-if” analysis was carried out to illustrate potential implications on grid reliability and resilience of reduced circuit breaker reliability. In a simple example it was found that, even with “worst-case” assumptions for the reliability of new SF₆-free switchgear technology compared to the current, the annual expected energy not supplied to grid users increased by only 5%. For more realistic power grids than in the example, with substation configurations with higher redundancy and including voltage levels below 400 kV, it is likely that the change will be even smaller.

The transition toward SF₆-free switchgear and offshore power system development is essential to achieve environmental objectives set by TSOs and society. However, this transition involves trade-offs: (1) the potential for introducing new vulnerabilities and increasing reliability risks, (2) the opportunity to phase out SF₆ and scale up offshore wind production, and (3) economic implications. Ultimately, advancing the energy transition requires TSOs and policymakers to make informed decisions about which risks are acceptable. The work conducted in MISSION WP1, as documented in this report, found no indications of significant technical risks to grid reliability and resilience associated with new switchgear technologies. Further investigation into economic and environmental risks will be addressed in upcoming tasks within MISSION WP1.

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7 APPENDIX A: SUPERCONDUCTING CABLE SYSTEMS

This appendix section will provide technical analysis in the form of excerpts from modeling studies [45], [21], [46] carried out by SuperNode and the University of Strathclyde. The reports were undertaken to understand the performance of superconductors in the power grid. In Table 2 in Section 2.3.2, use cases for superconducting cables in the grid of the future were introduced. For the purposes of electrical analysis, these can be refined into three topologies.

- Point to Point – See Appendix A Section 7.1
- Meshed conductors – See Appendix A Section 7.3
- Parallel conductor – See Appendix A Section 7.4

Electrical analysis for each of these topologies will be presented in the following sections. These analyses give input to the requirements of DC switchgear for superconducting transmission applications and also provide relevant information about the resilience of future power grids to faults on superconducting cables.

7.1 Point to Point HVDC Superconducting Cable Connection

A point-to-point HVDC Superconducting system can be used for a wide range of applications in a future grid. From the connection of large offshore or on shore renewable sites, to providing low-footprint, high-capacity expansion and reinforcement between sections of grid. Model and components

For this use case a point-to-point superconducting system was developed in PSCAD. The model consists of a bi-pole superconducting cable, connecting an offshore windfarm to an onshore grid. Modular multilevel converters (MMC) based converter stations are used to convert the windfarm power to DC for transmission on the SCS, and back to AC when connecting to the AC Grid. To allow the effects of DC faults to be analysed, no AC or DC circuit breakers were modelled in this simulation.

Figure 7-1. Point to Point connection representative circuit diagram

HTS Cable Model:

- Lumped π section model with resistance, inductance and capacitance per section. In this simulation each superconducting cable consists of 2, 100 km π sections.

Table 16: Point to Point Superconducting Cable Characteristics

Superconducting cable parameters	Value
Voltage	±100 kV
Power Capacity	2 GW
Cable Length	200 km
Current Rating	±10 kA
Critical Current	18.05 kA
Operating Temperature	65-77 K

Electrical System Parameters:

Table 17: Point to Point Equipment Characteristics

System Parameters	Value
MMC DC Voltage	±100 kV
MMC Rated Capacity	700 MVA
Offshore Transformer Voltage	66 kV/110 kV
Onshore Transformer Voltage	110 kV/400 kV

7.2 Fault Simulation

To show the performance of HTS Cables under fault conditions, two faults are simulated independently of each other on the cable. The fault locations are shown in the schematic in Figure 7-1.

- Fault 1: pole to pole fault at offshore head of HTS cable.
- Fault 2: pole to ground fault at midpoint of positive pole of HTS cable

7.2.1 Fault 1 pole to pole fault at offshore head of HTS cable.

A pole-to-pole fault is applied to the superconducting cable close to the offshore station at $t = 3$ s. As shown in Figure 7-2 the offshore station voltage quickly drops to 0, while the onshore voltage drops from ±100 kV to ±75 kV as shown in Figure 7-3. The resulting over current causes the arms in the MMC to block power flow.

Figure 7-2. Offshore converter station voltage during pole-to-pole fault

Figure 7-3. Onshore converter station voltage during pole-to-pole fault

The fault causes an over current of -20 kA on each pole of the superconducting cable, exceeding the critical current of 18.05 kA. As soon as the critical current is exceeded the superconducting cable quenches, i.e., as the superconductor cable transitions from its superconducting state its resistance and temperature rapidly increase. The increase in cable resistance has the effect of lowering the fault current, and as shown in Figure 7-4 the current in the HTS Cable rapidly falls to 0 after the initial fault current response.

Figure 7-4. Current, resistance and temperature on positive pole for pole-to-pole fault

7.2.2 Fault 2 pole to ground fault at midpoint of positive pole of HTS Cable

A pole to ground fault is applied to the positive pole of the HTS cable at $t = 3$ s. As shown in Figure 7-5, the voltage of the faulted pole drops to zero, while the voltage of the unaffected (negative) pole increases to -200 kV.

Figure 7-5. Offshore and Onshore converter station voltages pole-to-ground fault

As shown in Figure 7-6 the active power transmission remains stable in this simulation. In this simulation no overcurrent was observed on the superconducting cables. This can be understood by observing the change in the system voltage and understanding simplified relationship between power, current and voltage in a DC system where; power is equal to the product of the current and voltage. In this simulation the voltage in the system has increased while the current remains constant to allow

the same active power to be transmitted. However, despite there being no overcurrent condition in this scenario, the overvoltage observed on the healthy cable would need to be curtailed by the operation of circuit breakers in a real-world scenario. This would be achieved by operating circuit breakers.

Figure 7-6. Active Power during PtG Fault

7.2.3 Comparison with conventional HVDC Cable

As the previous two sections show, superconducting cables can rapidly reduce the fault current during a pole-to-pole fault, as well as remain operational during a pole to ground fault. With respect to the development of DC circuit breakers for integration with superconducting cables, as targeted by the MISSION project, the reduction of cable fault current is most relevant.

When compared to a similar fault on a typical HVDC cable, the inherent fault limiting capability of superconducting cables becomes clear. In Figure 7-7 the current at the onshore DC to AC inverter station is shown to be greater than 40 kA, twice the maximum of the fault current seen in the superconducting cable scenario. As discussed in section 7.2.1, unlike traditional cables the fault current in a superconducting cable is naturally limited due to the rapid rise in its resistance when its critical current is exceeded. Limiting the fault current in this way provides several advantages, including lower fault current clearing requirements for DC circuit breakers, allowing for traditional mechanical DCCB's, as mentioned in section 2.3.2.3 to potentially be used.

Figure 7-7. Cable fault currents for HVDC pole-to-pole fault

Incorporating superconducting cables into the grid in the future, can provide increased capacity in the event of faults, allowing time for fault clearing and the restoration of stable power transfer. This would contribute to strengthening the resilience of the grid. Additionally, the fault current limiting capability of superconducting cables, when compared to traditional HVDC cables, reduces the fault current that a DCCB would be required to interrupt.

7.3 Meshed HVDC Superconducting Cable System

A meshed grid offers alternative routes for power flow in the event of cable or equipment faults. In this case, a meshed network of high-capacity superconducting cables links offshore windfarms to the onshore AC network. The meshed system allows for the continued transfer of power to the onshore network in the event of cable faults.

7.3.1 Model and components

A four terminal, meshed, HVDC superconducting system was developed in PSCAD. The model consists of two offshore windfarms, connected to two onshore converter stations via a high capacity, meshed superconducting network. DC Circuit Breakers protect each terminal of the superconducting cables.

Figure 7-8. High capacity Meshed HVDC connection representative circuit diagram

HTS Cable Model:

- Lumped π section model with resistance, inductance and capacitance per section. In this simulation the superconducting cables under analysis were split into 3 π sections. The first section composes 5% of the total cable length, the second composes 90% of the cable length, and the third section composes the final 5% of the cable length.

Table 18: Meshed Superconducting Cable Characteristics

Superconducting cable parameters	Value
Voltage	± 100 kV
Power Capacity	2 GW
Cable Length	200 km
Current Rating	± 10 kA
Critical Current	18.05 kA
Operating Temperature	65-77 K

Electrical System Parameters

Table 19: Meshed Grid Converter Station Characteristics

Converter	Power Rating	DC Voltage	AC Voltage
MMC1	4000 MW	±100 kV	400 kV
MMC2	2000 MW	±100 kV	400 kV
MMC3	2000 MW	±100 kV	66 kV
MMC4	4000 MW	±100 kV	66 kV

7.3.2 Fault Simulation

A pole-to-pole fault is applied to the superconducting cable linking MMC1 and MMC4. The fault is applied to HTS 14 approximately 5% from the head of the cable near MMC4 as shown in Figure 7-8.

The DC fault occurs on cable HTS 14 at t=5s. As shown in Figure 7-9 the peak fault current is 23.6 kA, this is quickly interrupted by DCCB 41 at t = 5.006 s.

Figure 7-9. HTS 14 DCCB currents during pole-to-pole fault

When the DCCB activates and disconnects HTS 14, an active power transient occurs in the meshed grid. Figure 7-10 shows that the active power on HTS 14 drops from 0.56 GW to 0 GW. This deficit is transferred to the parallel healthy cable HTS 24, where the active power increases by 0.56 GW from 1.38 GW to 1.96 GW.

Figure 7-10. Active Power Transmission in HTS cables during pole-to-pole fault on HTS14

During the fault and resulting active power transient, the temperature of the first π section of HTS 14 spikes immediately following the fault, this is due to the fault current exceeding the 18.05 kA critical current of the superconducting cable. The unaffected sections of HTS14, as well HTS 24 remain constant at 77 K in the modelled π sections. The stable operating temperatures shown in Figure 7-11 show that the DCCB could prevent a quench in the unaffected sections of HTS 14, and that the increase in active power and current flow in HTS 24 was within its operating capacity.

Figure 7-11. Temperature of HST 14 and HTS 24 during pole-to-pole fault

7.3.3 Varying DCCB operation time to reduce fault current

In the scenario presented in the previous section, the DCCB with a detection delay of 2 ms clears the pole-to-pole fault in less than 10 ms. The maximum fault current was as high as 36.4 kA. However, by increasing the fault detection delay of the of the DCCB from 2 ms to 5 ms, the inherent fault current limiting ability of the superconducting cable can be leveraged to reduce the fault current.

Figure 7-12 shows fault current on HTS 14 with the same pole to pole fault as before but with a 5 ms delay on the DCCB. The fault current rises to above 24 kA, far exceeding the 18.05 kA critical current of the superconducting cable. As a result, the superconducting cable quenches, rapidly increasing its resistance. This causes the fault current to deteriorate, and when the DCCB interrupts the fault at $t = 5.007$ s the fault current has fallen to 4.4 kA within the capabilities of state-of-the-art circuit breaker technology

Figure 7-12. Fault Current with 5 ms DCCB Delay

As with the previous simulation, an active power transient occurs in the network, with the power originally transmitted by HTS 14, now transmitted by HTS 24 as shown in Figure 7-13.

Figure 7-13. Active Power Transmission during pole-to-pole Fault on HTS14 with 5 ms DCCB delay

As the DCCB operating time is delayed and the fault current is allowed to propagate the temperature increase in the first π section of HTS 14 exceeds 450 K. However, the temperature regresses to normal operating conditions of 77 K a short time after the fault is cleared. The remaining sections of HTS 14, and the health HTS 24 see no change in operating temperature.

Figure 7-14. Temperature of HST 14 and HTS 24 during point-to-point fault with 5 ms DCCB delay

7.4 Parallel HVDC Superconducting Cable Connections

Similar to a point-to-point system, but with parallel superconducting cables. These cables can provide a high-capacity link between grid sections and can provide continuity of service of the superconducting system in the event of a fault on one cable.

7.4.1 Model and components

The University of Strathclyde, SuperNode and the ORE Catapult carried out a study [46] on the technical challenges related to decarbonising the grid. As part of this confidential study, a model was developed in which an existing onshore AC grid was linked proposed offshore DC grid in a hybrid AC/DC system. The onshore AC network was modelled on a real-world grid, while the offshore network was modelled as a DC grid made up of superconducting cables connecting offshore wind generation sites and interconnectors to other EU countries to the AC grid.

The offshore DC grid was split into an upper and lower section, with both sections featuring wind generation sites and interconnectors to other grids. The upper and lower sections were connected together with a HTS cable providing a high-capacity connection for power flow between the sections, and to provide an alternative route for power flow if required due to a fault or equipment maintenance.

For the purposes of this analysis, the cable linking the two sections of the offshore DC network will be subjected to a fault at the midpoint of the superconducting cable. Two cases with different topologies will be analysed, Case 1 with a single conductor and Case 2 with two parallel conductors.

Figure 7-15 shows Case 1 where the upper and lower sections of the grid are connected by a single cable between converter 4 and converter 6.

Figure 7-15. Single Superconducting Cable

7.4.2 Fault Simulation

In both cases, a pole-to-pole fault is applied to the middle of the HTS cable. The DCCBs are set to only interrupt a fault after a 10 ms delay.

7.4.2.1 Case 1 Single Superconducting Cable

The DC Current of the HTS cable in Case 1 is shown in Figure 7-16. At $t = 0.5$ seconds a fault occurs causing the current to rapidly rise to over 25 kA. This exceeds the 22.5 kA critical current of the HTS cable causing a quench. As the DC circuit breaker is operating with a 10 ms delay, the fault current decays from this value before being safely interrupted and reaching 0 kA.

Figure 7-16. Fault on Single Superconducting Cable

7.4.2.2 Case 2 Single Superconducting Cable

In case two, two parallel conductors are used to connect the upper and lower sections of the offshore grid. The parallel connection between converter 4 and converter 6 is shown in Figure 7-17.

Figure 7-17. Parallel Superconducting Cables

The pole-to-pole fault occurs on one of the cables, and the midpoint between each converter. Figure 7-18 shows that at $t = 5$ s the fault causes the current in the affected cable to spike from 6 kA to 10 kA (below the critical current), before dropping to 0 kA.

Figure 7-18. DC current in faulted parallel cable

Figure 7-19 shows that at the beginning of the simulation, the healthy superconducting cable is operating with a steady state current of 6 kA. At the time of the fault, $t = 5$ s the DC current begins to rise steadily in the superconducting cable reaching a new steady state of 12 kA.

Figure 7-19. DC current in healthy parallel cable

7.4.2.3 Built in redundancy

When comparing the results of Case 1 and Case 2 it becomes clear that a parallel superconducting cable provides built in redundancy in the event of a fault. The current and power flow in the affected cable is safely transferred to the healthy cable, with no interruption of service of the superconducting system. The increased capacity of the superconducting cable provides resilience and would allow the network to remain functional while repairs to the faulty cable are performed.

8 APPENDIX B: CIRCUIT BREAKER SCENARIOS

8.1 Methodology

8.1.1 High voltage population estimate

The Open Infrastructure Database [1], illustrated in Figure 8-1, is used to obtain and estimate of the number of lines, substations and transformers in Norway, Germany, France and Spain. Each substation is registered as an object with a geographical location and perimeter (a polygon with geographical coordinates). For all substations, the following is counted:

- The number of outside lines terminating inside the substation, i.e. crossing the perimeter (this excludes small line stubs inside the substation), along with their rated voltage.
- The number of transformer windings and their rated voltage

Railway networks have not been counted.

Figure 8-1. Snapshots of the Open Infrastructure Map (<https://openinframap.org/>)

By summing the data for all substations, the total number of line ends and transformer windings are obtained. Factors in Table 20 and Table 21 are then used to estimate the number of circuit breakers.

Table 20: Average number of circuit breakers per line end

Voltage	Norway	Germany	France	Spain
52 kV < U ≤ 75 kV	1	1	1	1
75 kV < U ≤ 145 kV	1	1	1	1
145 kV < U ≤ 245 kV	1	1	1	1
245 kV < U ≤ 300 kV	1,5	1	1	1,5
300 kV < U ≤ 420 kV	2	1	1	1,5

Table 21: Average number of circuit breakers per transformer winding

Voltage	Norway	Germany	France	Spain
52 kV < U ≤ 75 kV	1	1	1	1
75 kV < U ≤ 145 kV	1	1	1	1
145 kV < U ≤ 245 kV	1	1	1	1
245 kV < U ≤ 300 kV	1,5	1	1	1,5
300 kV < U ≤ 420 kV	2	1	1	1,5

In addition, some circuit breakers are assumed to be present in the substation, for example to switch reactive components and between bus bars. These components are not readily obtained from the database, but the factors in Table 22 can be tuned to achieve a reasonable population estimate.

Table 22: Average number of circuit breakers per voltage level in a substation (for reactive components and bus bars)

Voltage	Norway	Germany	France	Spain
52 kV < U ≤ 75 kV	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
75 kV < U ≤ 145 kV	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
145 kV < U ≤ 245 kV	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
245 kV < U ≤ 300 kV	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5
300 kV < U ≤ 420 kV	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5

Once the circuit breaker population is estimated in each of the four countries, the results are summed together, and the total European population is estimated as being 2.5 times larger. The factor 2.5 is based on the sizes of the five power systems, see Table 23.

Table 23: Yearly load in Norway, Germany, France, Spain and Europe

NOR	GER	FRA	ESP	EUR	$\frac{EUR}{NOR + GER + FRA + ESP}$
135 TWh	460 TWh	430 TWh	230 TWh	3140 TWh	2.5

8.1.2 Medium voltage population estimate

The Open Infrastructure database is limited in its registration of medium voltage. Based on the feedback from the partners during the first iteration of the scenario development it was concluded that the MV population is likely underestimated when using this database. The MV population is difficult to obtain due to the lack of power system databases for this level, and the WP1 partners are not in a position to verify the estimates. Therefore, a different approach has been applied to obtain estimates for the MV population. The MV population estimate is obtained by using existing estimates.

T&D Europe’s report was published in March 2020 [2]. It estimates medium voltage (1-52 kV) primary and secondary switchgear in Europe (the exact definition of “Europe” is not given, but the estimates are very rough):

- “The order of magnitude of installed base of primary functional units in Europe is estimated with 1 to 2 million. Typical SF6 quantities are between 2 and 3 kg for GIS and between 0.1 and 0.6 kg for AIS equipped with SF6 circuit-breakers.”

Table 24: Primary MV switchgear as estimated by T&D Europe [2]

Primary switchgear					
SIS (< 5 %)		GIS (30 %)		AIS (65 %)	
Insulating medium	Breaking medium	Insulating medium	Breaking medium	Insulating medium	Breaking medium
Epoxy: 100 %	Vacuum: 100 %	SF ₆ : 100 %	Vacuum: 90 % SF ₆ : 10 %	Air: 100 %	Vacuum: 70 % SF ₆ : 30 %

The medium voltage results in this report will be based on the primary switchgear estimates by T&D Europe.

8.1.3 Circuit breaker characteristics and SF6 contents

The following steps have been taken to obtain realistic input data:

1. The TSOs in the project have provided some data on their average SF6 contents for circuit breakers at selected voltage levels. Siemens have provided data on state-of-the-art components. Additional sources have been used to augment the data whenever possible, such as T&D Europe’s [2] estimated SF6 contents in the medium voltage population.
2. The circuit breaker population is assumed to consist of four main age groups: CBs aged 20+ years, CBS aged 10-20 years, CBs aged 0-10 years, and CBs commissioned in the future. The two latter are assumed to be state-of-the-art CBs.

For each voltage level, a certain share of the population is assumed to be AIS or GIS CBs. Efforts have also been made to adapt the circuit breaker characteristics to each country. See Figure 8-2.

The SF6 contents in circuit breakers are specified as function of type (AIS vs GIS), voltage, age and country. See Figure 8-3. For HV AIS it has been assumed that 20% of bays are equipped with SF6-

based instrument transformers, and that these instrument transformers contain twice as much SF6 as the circuit breaker itself. The values in Figure 8-3 are the resulting average amounts of SF6 per bay, with circuit breakers and instrument transformers contributing with approximately 70% and 30% of the total amount, respectively.

The reported SF6 contents in CBs vary greatly for each TSO in MISSION, but the SF6 contents are chosen to be typical for Europe as a whole and not specified for each of the four countries. Therefore, the estimated inventory of SF6 cannot be calibrated for each individual country. The TSOs in the project are also not able to provide data for all the voltage levels, so some educated guesses have been required.

Yearly average leaks are assumed to be somewhere in the range 0.3-0.9%, with 0.3% representing the absolute best practice for state-of-the-art and future circuit breakers. This applies to both AIS and GIS. End-of-life (EOL) emissions have been included to account for losses in the gas recycling and disposal, and these are assumed to be independent of the age of the circuit breakers. For HV the EOL-emissions are assumed to be 1%, while 1.5% are assumed for MV according to [3]. See Figure 8-4 for SF6 emissions input data.

Figure 8-2. Share of AIS and GIS in Norway, Germany, France and Spain

Figure 8-3. SF6 contents per bay

Figure 8-4. Nominal SF6 emissions

8.2 Scenario calculations

8.2.1 Expected population growth

To calculate the expected population growth, it is postulated that it is roughly correlated to the system size (measured in yearly delivered TWh). ENTSO-E has developed scenarios for this parameter in their TYNDP 2024 [4], predicting the growth in Europe as a whole. The “Distributed Energy” scenario is used as it best accounts for the excess network growth arising from more distributed generation. The emphasis on European energy independence is also considered to be a more realistic scenario than the more “globalized” system considered in the scenario “Global Ambition”.

Based on feedback from the partners in WP1, a different growth curve has been developed for Germany’s transmission system. The forecasts by 50Hertz predict a very modest growth in the electric load (i.e. little electrification, which for example characterizes Norway’s system [5]), but a very large growth in the system over the next 10-15 years to accommodate a total shift from centralized to distributed generation. The curve assumes a 50% increase by 2035, and a 1% yearly increase from 2035-2050. Figure 8-5 shows the two different growth curves.

Figure 8-5. Growth curves for the circuit breaker population

By applying the ENTSO-E growth curve to all voltage groups except for the German transmission system, Figure 8-6 shows the resulting future growth in the European distribution and transmission system circuit breaker population. The transmission system population is estimated to grow by 56% in 2050 on average, while the distribution system population grows by 43%. For comparison, [3] estimated the medium voltage population to increase by 42% in 2050, though relative to 2020. The IEA has estimated the total route length of the distribution and transmission system to increase by 33% and 69% in 2050, respectively.

Figure 8-6. Resulting growth for the European circuit breaker population at Distribution and Transmission levels

8.2.2 Decommissioning of existing circuit breakers

Two main strategies for transitioning to SF6-free circuit breakers have been defined. These two strategies are based on two distinct approaches to decommissioning and replacing existing circuit breakers. In the “Business as usual” strategy, all circuit breakers are allowed to reach their natural end-of-life before they are replaced. The service life of a circuit breaker is calculated based on the assumption that it follows a normal distribution with an expected lifetime of 35 years. The standard deviation is set to 5 years, resulting in 99.7% of circuit breakers having a service life of 20-50 years. A second decommissioning strategy is the more aggressive “SF6-free by 2050”, in which an SF6-free population is obtained in 2050 by replacing all SF6-based circuit breakers. This strategy will involve prematurely decommissioning circuit breakers, thereby reducing SF6 emissions at the expense of added circuit breakers.

For both strategies it is assumed that SF6-free alternatives will become available according to Table 25, and that all circuit breakers commissioned after this point will be SF6-free. Note that the table indicates when SF6-free components are available in unlimited quantities. In the voltage groups where SF6-free alternatives are already available and in use, a linear ramp-up of the SF6-free share of circuit breakers will be assumed.

Table 25: Timeline indicating when no new SF6-based circuit breakers will be commissioned

Voltage	SF6-free options available (in unlimited quantities)
$U \leq 52 \text{ kV}$	2026
$52 \text{ kV} < U \leq 75 \text{ kV}$	2028
$75 \text{ kV} < U \leq 145 \text{ kV}$	2028
$145 \text{ kV} < U \leq 245 \text{ kV}$	2032
$245 \text{ kV} < U \leq 300 \text{ kV}$	2032
$300 \text{ kV} < U \leq 420 \text{ kV}$	2032

For both strategies it is necessary to know how fast the existing and future circuit breaker population will decay in size. For a group of circuit breakers commissioned today, the number of circuit breakers remaining in operation at a given time in the future is calculated from their expected lifetime. Figure 8-7 summarizes the three key functions describing the circuit breaker lifetime:

- $f(\mu, \sigma; x)$ the probability density function, here shown with $\mu = 35$ and $\sigma = 5$
- $\Phi(\mu, \sigma; x)$ the cumulative probability function, describing the probability of a circuit breaker being decommissioned by year x
- $Q(\mu, \sigma; x)$ the survivor function (simply $1 - \Phi(\mu, \sigma; x)$), indicating the probability of a circuit breaker remaining in operation for at least x years

Figure 8-7. Normal distribution ($\mu = 35$ years and $\sigma = 5$ years) describing the lifetime of a circuit breaker

For a group of N circuit breakers commissioned at the same time, $N \cdot Q(x)$ is the number remaining in operation in year x . For circuit breakers commissioned in the future, this function is then used to calculate their gradual decommissioning rate.

The same approach can be used to calculate the decommissioning rate of the existing circuit breakers population, but it requires knowledge of their age. With the three age groups defined earlier, the timeline in Figure 8-8 is constructed based on the assumption that a fixed number of circuit breakers have been commissioned during each of the three periods (this is not known, but it is the neutral assumption given the lack of other information):

Figure 8-8. Assumed timeline for commissioning of circuit breakers in the past

With no new breakers commissioned after $x = 0$ (we only study the existing circuit breaker population and its future decay), $R(x)$ circuit breakers remain in operation in year $x > 0$:

$$R(x) = \gamma \sum_{k=x}^{x+9} Q(k) + \beta \sum_{k=x+10}^{x+19} Q(k) + \alpha \sum_{k=x+20}^{50} Q(k)$$

The factors α , β and γ are not known, but can be calculated based on the known age distribution of the present-day population. Assuming that A p.u. of the present-day population are aged 20+ years, B p.u. are aged 10-19 years, and Y p.u. are aged 0-9 years (and that $A + B + Y = 1$ p.u.), then one obtains:

$$A = \alpha \sum_{k=20}^{50} Q(k)$$

$$B = \beta \sum_{k=10}^{19} Q(k)$$

$$Y = \gamma \sum_{k=0}^9 Q(k)$$

Rough estimates for A , B and Y are obtained from IEA’s report “Electricity Grids and Secure Energy Transitions”, in which the age composition of the European transmission and distribution systems are estimated. These estimates result in the parameter values in Table 26.

Table 26: Factors used to describe the age composition of the distribution and transmission system in Europe

Parameter	Transmission	Distribution
A	0.45	0.5
B	0.25	0.25
Y	0.3	0.25

Using these numbers, the decay of the transmission system and distribution system population are shown in Figure 8-9.

Figure 8-9. Estimated development of the present-day circuit breaker population

The “Business as usual” strategy is calculated based on these curves. By considering the three age groups separately, the impact of different properties for circuit breakers in these groups can be accounted for (e.g. older circuit breakers having more SF6 and higher leaks).

For the “SF6-free by 2050” strategy, all the SF6-free CBs will follow the curves in Figure 8-9. The SF6-based circuit breakers will be decommissioned at a constant rate (a fixed number each year). This forced decommissioning begins when SF6-free alternatives are available in unlimited quantities, avoiding the commissioning of many new SF6-based circuit breakers which will have to be decommissioned again by 2050. Of the excess circuit breakers, the oldest are decommissioned first, removing circuit breakers with higher SF6-amounts and leaks early and maximizing the utilization of circuit breaker lifetime. However, a majority of the excess circuit breakers (i.e. those that are expected to still be in operation in 2050 if not decommissioned prematurely) will be relatively new.

8.3 Appendix references

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9 APPENDIX C: GRID RELIABILITY AND RESILIENCE

9.1 Quantitative assessment of resilience related to AC circuit breakers

This appendix gives some additional details on the methodology and data used for the quantitative assessment of grid reliability and resilience. The methodology includes a calculation of consequences in the grid in terms of power supply interruptions, described in Section 9.1.1, which is used as inputs to the calculation of reliability of supply indices, outlined in Section 9.1.2. The test system used for the simulation example is specified in Section 9.1.3.

9.1.1 Consequence calculation using security constrained optimal power flow

As part of a quantitative analysis, the consequences of outages should be mapped. The first step is a security constrained optimal power flow (SCOPF) that finds a plausible base operating state for the power system case. In the second step, the operating point is fixed and the consequences after outages of system components are calculated.

A description of the first step of SCOPF formulation follows. For the purposes of this study, a DC approximation of the power flow equations is appropriate. This approximation is based on a few assumptions that usually hold for extra and high-voltage parts of the power system yielding linear power flow equations. The DC power flow can be formulated as

$$B \cdot \theta = P$$

where B is the susceptance matrix, θ is the bus voltage angles, and P is the injected power at each bus. This equation binds the voltage angles to the injected power for each bus, thus modeling the active power flow in the system.

The equation is used in the SCOPF for modeling the base operating state and is also used to include the flow after all N-1 branch contingencies in the system, the contingency security constraints. With these constraints the system state is considered safe (no load shedding) for any single branch contingency.

Constraints are added to the base operating state such that the components are used within their operating limits. Generators have limits for active power, the load shedding must be within actual load at the bus, there is set a maximum angle change limit of branches, branches have a set capacity limit where specified. All these limits are enforced in the base operating state and for all contingency states.

The objective function of the SCOPF is to minimize the cost of generation $c(P_0)$ where P_0 are the decision variables are for the generation. The generation cost is a value per MW for each generator.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Min } c(P_0) \\
 \text{s. t. } & F_0 = \frac{(\theta_f - \theta_t)}{x_i}, & f, t \in M, i \in L \\
 & \theta_f - \theta_t < \overline{\Delta\theta}, & f, t \in M \\
 & -\overline{F}_0 < F_0 < \overline{F}_0 \\
 & F_0 \cdot A = P_0 - P_D \\
 & 0 \leq P_0 \leq \overline{P}_0 \\
 & G_k(x_0) \geq g_k, & k \in K
 \end{aligned}$$

Where M is the set of buses in the system, L is the set of branches in the system, a bar marks the limit of a variable, F_0 is the power flow on the branches, x_i is the reactance of line i , A is a connectivity matrix connecting branches and nodes, P_D is the demand for each node. The equation models the different constraints for each of the contingency cases $k \in K$. The constraints for the contingency cases are similar to the base case, but where components on contingency are removed.

After the base operating state is found in step one, the consequences are calculated in step two as described in the following. The SCOPF formulated for determining the base operating state is changed for the consequence calculations. Branch limits are removed, as the thermal limits of branches can temporarily be extended in contingency situations, but not the maximum angle change limit of branches. In addition, the branch, generator, load, or a combination of those are removed as described by each outage event.

The objective function is changed in the second step to only minimize load shedding, while the maximum generation for each generator is set to the base operating state.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Min } c(\ell_k) \\
 \text{s. t. } & F_k = \frac{(\theta_f - \theta_t)}{x_i}, & f, t \in M, i \in L \\
 & \theta_f - \theta_t < \overline{\Delta\theta}, & f, t \in M \\
 & -\overline{F}_k < F_k < \overline{F}_k \\
 & F_k \cdot A = P_k - P_D + \ell_k \\
 & P_k = P_0
 \end{aligned}$$

where ℓ_c is the load shedding for contingency k . The optimization is evaluated for every contingency k in the contingency set K .

9.1.2 Quantitative reliability and resilience simulation logic

This subchapter gives a high-level description of the quantitative reliability and resilience simulation logic. The logic of the simulation is based on the understanding of a system unit, here referred to as a Power System Unit (PSU), as defined by ENTSO-E [40], as a “group of components which fulfils a main function in the power system”, delimited by circuit breakers. This simplifies the modelling of the power system as a graph: The PSUs makes up the nodes of the graph, while the Circuit Breakers (CB) of the Fault Clearance System (FCS) makes up the edges of the graph.

The simulation algorithm follows a set of nested steps, following a sequence of events:

1. An initial failure of either a PSU or an FCS is simulated.
2. A dependent FCS reaction is simulated if the initial failure is that of a PSU.
3. A second independent failure of a PSU or an FCS in the outage duration of previous events is simulated.

At each step several calculations are performed:

- The state of in-service PSUs is assessed by identifying failed PSUs, or healthy PSUs which are isolated from the system due to an open CB.
- The failure frequency of the event at the current step is calculated based on the failure frequency of the initial failure, multiplied by the probability of consequent events (step 2 and 3 events).
- The outage duration of the event at its current step is calculated. The event is considered ended when a PSU which is either failed or otherwise isolated either due to the current or previous events is connected back into service.

This simulation logic is illustrated in Figure 9-1 using the IEEE 5-bus test system. Looking at the left-hand side of the figure: An initial failure of the PSU overhead transmission line *AE* occurs (numbered by the red text “1” in the figure). The outage duration of this initial event is the repair time of line *AE*. The initial failure triggers a dependent reaction. In this example, the CB between line *AE* and bus *E* experience missing operation, and the backup CB between bus *E* and line *ED* opens, isolating the healthy line *ED* from the system. On the other side of the initial failure, the CB between line *AE* and bus *A* reacts correctly, but non-selective reaction of the backup protection system between bus *A* and *AB* reacts, thus isolating the healthy line *AB*. The outage duration of this second step is from the initial dependent reaction, until the first PSU affected by this is back in service due to the switching time of the CB between bus *A* and *AB*. A second independent failure of line *CD* is simulated in the timespan of the previous outage. The outage duration of the event associated with this step is also ended by the change in system state due to the *A/AB* CB re-closing. The outage duration is thus defined by a change in component states. The right-hand side of the figure shows which PSUs and CBs are affected by the different steps in the simulation.

Figure 9-1. Simulation logic, step by step. PSU states at different times, and a corresponding single line diagram.

One such series of simulation steps is considered one iteration of the algorithm. Results are collected for each iteration and parsed to find the expected failure frequency and outage duration of different contingencies (defined by PSU states) after an appropriate number of simulations is performed.

9.1.3 Test system specifications

For the purpose of quantitatively illustrating the impact on reliability on a power system level, a small 400 kV test system was chosen. The test system specifications are based on a well-known 5-bus test system used for economic studies [42]. The voltage level of this test system was increased from 230 kV to 400 kV to make it more relevant for the HVAC circuit breaker technology developed in the MISSION project. With the increased voltage level, the power handling capacity of the system was also increased. The single-line diagram of the system, including circuit breakers, is shown in Figure 9-2. The system specifications are given in Chapter 9.1.3.

Figure 9-2. IEEE 5-bus test system [42].

The technical data available for the 5-bus system and typical line parameters were used to increase voltage and capacity. The assumed reactance for the 230 kV overhead lines in the system was $0.3125 \Omega/\text{km}$ (from $0.5 \Omega/\text{mile}$). The line parameters were replaced by overhead lines with resistance $0.02 \Omega/\text{km}$, inductance $0.8532 \text{ mH}/\text{km}$, and rated current 3555 A . The maximum angle difference over the line is equal as the original data suggest, 30° .

Table 27: Line parameters

From bus	To bus	R [pu]	X [pu]	Length [km]
1	2	0.00439	0.05884	351.25
1	4	0.00475	0.06366	380.0
1	5	0.00100	0.01340	80.0
2	3	0.00169	0.02262	135.0
3	4	0.00464	0.06219	371.25
4	5	0.00464	0.06219	371.25

Table 28: Bus parameters

Bus	1	2	3	4	5
Type	PV	PQ	PV	Slack	PV
Demand [MW]	0	800	800	1100	0

Table 29: Generator parameters

Generator	1	2	3	4	5
Bus	1	1	3	4	5
Capacity [MW]	120	510	1560	600	1800
Cost [\$/MW]	14	15	30	40	10

9.2 Additional circuit breaker and grid reliability statistics

This section supplements the overview in Section 4.3.3 of relevant statistics. Table 30 reproduces statistics from ENTSO-E [38] on the number of component faults in different countries and shows the share of all faults that were circuit breaker faults and protection and control system faults, respectively. (Note that in these ENTSO-E statistics the latter component group is denoted control system and could include other components than protection (and control) system equipment.) Table 31 reproduces statistics on the share of the total energy not supplied (ENS) in each country that was due to faults on circuit breakers and protection and control systems, respectively. Both sets of statistics only include faults on components at 100 kV and above.

Table 30: Percentage allocation of faults during 2014–2023 by component type [38].

Country	Circuit breakers	Protection and control system
Estonia	6%	11%
Latvia	2%	14%
Lithuania	3%	10%
Denmark	3%	13%
Finland	1%	6%
Iceland	4%	12%
Norway	4%	20%
Sweden	2%	11%

Table 31: Percentage allocation of ENS by component type over 2014–2023 [38].

Country	Circuit breakers	Protection and control system
Estonia	11%	22%
Latvia	0%	55%
Lithuania	5%	26%
Denmark	7%	21%
Finland	4%	7%
Iceland	5%	13%
Norway	4%	23%
Sweden	4%	8%

9.3 Qualitative FMEA analysis for superconducting systems

This section supplements the discussion in Section 4.2 about superconducting cables. In January 2025 SuperNode, in collaboration with participants from a national TSO, third level institutes, and a business consultancy undertook a workshop to develop an FMEA for a potential use case in a terrestrial environment for a superconducting systems (SCS) project. The current SuperNode SCS design (as of Q1 2025) as well as future design and qualification plans were reviewed to identify high risk system components. Actions to mitigate these risks were proposed and include advanced monitoring capabilities and improved installation methods.

9.3.1 Components of the SuperNode superconducting cable system design

This section provides further information on the components of the superconducting cable system (SCS) proposed by SuperNode and introduced in Figure 2-5. This figure is also reproduced below (Figure 9-3) for easy reference.

Figure 9-3. Components of a superconducting cable system as proposed by SuperNode.

The 25 km length of SCS is composed of five superconducting cable sections. The sections are connected together via field joints. These cryostat joints have been designed to facilitate the flow of LN2 between cable sections while also maintaining electrical continuity between them. At discrete points along the SCS transmission length, re-cooling and re-pressurisation of the LN2 may be required.

A subsea Cooling & Pumping Station (CPS) will be connected to the SCS through a CPS Joint at these locations.

To allow the SCS to interface with other grid infrastructure and facilitate power transfer to traditional switch gear and conductors, SuperNode is developing a high-capacity hybrid HTS-Copper termination. This component provides the function of terminating HTS tapes to an appropriately sized copper bus, whilst maintaining thermal and dielectric integrity. The termination also allows for the removal or introduction of LN2 into the cable system.

9.3.2 Methodology and TRL in Context evaluation

Key risks involve first-of-a-kind components e.g., superconducting-to-copper termination interfaces (as shown in Figure 2-5) that require significant development in future phases. Other operational components like pumps, valves, instrumentation and monitoring systems, vacuum systems and cryogenic systems, though not explicitly high-risk, still warrant consideration and were considered in a TRL in Context evaluation.

A TRL in Context evaluation considers the technical maturity of components within the SCS. Some industry standard components have high TRL levels when considered in isolation. However, when integrated into subsystems of the SCS such as a cable joint or cooling and pumping station, their TRL level in context lowers. The delta between TRL Level in isolation and TRL Level in Context was a key indicator in the analysis highlights low-maturity, first-of-a-kind, high-risk components and their associated risks.

Taking guidance from [47] , the workshop provided high-level overview of system functions, failure modes, failure effects, and criticality. As an example, consider and TRL9 industry standard component. e.g. a high voltage electrical termination. These are widely used grid infrastructure components and by themselves have a high level of maturity in terms of both risk understanding and installation and maintenance methods. However, once a termination is integrated into the SCS the TRL level in Context drops significantly as it is now required to interface with non-industry standard components such as HTS-tape to copper transition end plugs, and components which facilitate the transition from cryogenic to ambient temperatures.

9.3.3 SCS Specific Example (designed specifically for SCS)

A further example of a component that is designed specifically for the SCS is an LN2 breakout joint. A critical operating condition for superconductivity in the SCS is the temperature of the LN2 Cryogen. Maintaining the temperature of the cryogen at or below 77 K along the length of the SCS is essential as an increase beyond this could cause issues such as localised hotspots on the HTS Conductors leading to a quench. This would result in temporary or even total loss of transmission.

The temperature of the cryogen is maintained using advanced cryostat technology, state of the art class insulation materials, vacuum pumping and the periodic removal, recooling and repumping of the cryogen in a cooling and pumping station (CPS).

This is achieved by LN2 Breakout Joints, which are designed to allow both the continuation of current flow and to facilitate the removal of LN2 from the inner cryostat.

Continuation of current flow is achieved by bonding the HTS tapes of the SCS to a copper end plug which interfaces with a large copper bus within the joint housing. Simultaneously the LN2 flow from the inner cryostat is diverted out of the SCS and into a cooling and pumping station (CPS) where it is recooled to below 77 K, repressurised and recirculated into the inner cryostat.

Failure in the breakout joint could cause localised arcing or tracking due to a poor electrical interface. Alternatively, failure to contain the LN2 could result in a loss of coolant flow and pressure, or leaks to the surrounding environment.

Although the FMEA study highlighted these as priority risks due to the potential for transmission interruption. Management and mitigation can be achieved by training skilled installers, pre and post installation checks, instrumentation, preventative inspection, scheduled replacement cycles and dedicated temperature monitoring.

9.3.4 Conclusion

Although the FMEA highlighted a number of key novel components which when considered by TRL in context present as a potential high-level risk, the maturity of these combined individual components, the engineering, test, qualification and redundancy built in have mitigated the concerns regarding the resilience of the superconducting cable system.